

Quantum geometry of a tetrahedron at the ground and near excited states

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Abstract

Following a series of lectures about LQG (loop quantum gravity) held by L. Fatibene (Department of Mathematics, University of Torino (Italy)) in Q1 2024, in this laboratory we will describe the quantum geometry of space at the Planck scale. We will work out the spin network representing a tetrahedron at the ground and near excited states and calculate the observables measuring the related geometric properties.

We will show that at the ground state a tetrahedron is a qubit, that is a linear combination of two basic quantum states. Moreover, the squared volume basis exhibits two tetrahedra, of which one is the reflection of the other against one of the faces. At the near excited states the dimension of the invariant isotropic subspace increases and a tetrahedron can not be described as a qubit any more. The expected trend in the reduction of the fuzziness with the excitation is glimpsed as well.

1 Introduction

In Q1 2024 L. Fatibene (Department of Mathematics, University of Torino (Italy)) held an extensive series of lectures about LQG (loop quantum gravity), refer to [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9]. The series culminated in the representation of the quantum properties of geometry in space.

As an application, in this laboratory we will focus on the quantum geometry of a tetrahedron at the fundamental representation and close ones, formulating the relevant invariant isotropic subspace, calculating the observables in terms of expectation value and standard deviation.

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2 LQG picture

2.1 Dual representation

Let's consider the geometric picture of a tetrahedron. In figure 1 the tetrahedron is outlined and the faces labeled. A face is labeled against the opposite vertex.

Figure 1: Outline of a tetrahedron

Let's now move to the dual representation, refer to [6]. A tetrahedron is represented as a node and each face as a link γ delimited by the node at one end. Description is in figure 2, where the links are depicted as incoming to the node.

Figure 2: Dual representation of a tetrahedron

2.2 Hilbert spaces in LQG

As per [7], a brief recall of the Hilbert spaces in LQG.

Let's have an irreducible representation $\rho^{(j)} : SU(2) \rightarrow GL(V_{(j)})$, where the semi-integer j is the spin of the representation, $V_{(j)}$ is the support vector space of dimension $2j + 1$, $V_{(j)}^*$ its dual, $e_\alpha \in V_{(j)}$ a basis, $e^\beta \in V_{(j)}^*$ its dual basis. So, a group element $U \in SU(2)$ can be represented as a tensor $\rho^{(j)}(U)^\alpha_\beta e_\alpha \otimes e^\beta \in V_{(j)} \otimes V_{(j)}^*$.

Let's define a group representation $Sym^n : SU(2) \rightarrow GL(\mathbb{C}^{n+1})$ as the symmetrized tensor product of n copies of the fundamental representation $\rho^{(1/2)} : SU(2) \rightarrow GL(2, \mathbb{C}) : U \rightarrow U_B^A$, let's choose a symmetrized tensor product $e_{A_1} \odot \dots \odot e_{A_n} \in \mathbb{C}^{n+1}$ as a basis; so we have $Sym^n(U) : \mathbb{C}^{n+1} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{n+1}$ as $Sym^n(U) = U_{(B_1)}^{(A_1)} \dots U_{(B_n)}^{(A_n)} e_{A_1} \odot \dots \odot e_{A_n} \odot e^{B_1} \odot \dots \odot e^{B_n}$. Hence we have $\rho^{(j)} = Sym^{2j}$, i.e. $j = n/2$.

Let's have an abstract lattice $\Gamma = (N, L)$, with N nodes and L links, each link being a pair of nodes, $l = (s_l, t_l)$, called the source node and the target node of the link, respectively. To any link $l \in L$, with a spin j , we associate the vector space $V_l = V_{(j)} \otimes V_{(j)}^*$. A node $\nu \in N$ acts as a source node for outgoing links and as a target node for incoming links. To any node ν , we associate a vector space $V_\nu = V_{(j_1)} \otimes \dots \otimes V_{(j_h)} \otimes V_{(j_1)}^* \otimes \dots \otimes V_{(j_k)}^*$, where j_1, \dots, j_h are the spins of the incoming links, and j_1, \dots, j_k are the spins of the outgoing links.

Let's associate to the lattice the space of functionals $\psi : SU(2)^L \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ as $\psi = i(c)$, where the cylindric tensor c is defined as $\rho^{(j_1)}(U)_{\beta_1}^{\alpha_1} \dots \rho^{(j_l)}(U)_{\beta_l}^{\alpha_l} e_{\alpha_1} \otimes \dots \otimes e_{\alpha_l} \otimes e^{\beta_1} \otimes \dots \otimes e^{\beta_l} \in V_{(\Gamma, j_l)}$, and the intertwiner i is a covector $\in V_{(\Gamma, j_l)}^*$. Spin networks are invariant states, which require $i \in Inv(V_{(\Gamma, j_l)}^*)$, and constitute the Hilbert spaces of LQG.

2.3 Operators

As for operators, they describe observables and, when applied to quantum states, return a relevant measure of the physical state. As per [7], [8], and indicating again a link with a γ , we have the following basic Lie operators

$$\begin{aligned} (L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_a &= -T\rho^{(j)}(\tau_a) \quad \text{to the right of the representation if } \gamma \text{ is incoming} \\ &\text{or} \\ &= T\rho^{(j)}(\tau_a) \quad \text{to the left of the representation if } \gamma \text{ is outgoing} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\tau_a = -\frac{i}{2}\sigma_a$ (Pauli matrices), $a = x, y, z$; $j = \text{spin of the representation}$.

Moreover we have

$$C_{(\nu)} = \sum_{\gamma} (L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_a = 0 \quad \text{quantum closure condition} \quad (2)$$

Applied to an intertwiner

$$\begin{aligned} (L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_a e^\alpha &= -T\rho^{(j)}(\tau_a)_\mu^\alpha e^\mu \quad \gamma \text{ outgoing} \\ &\text{or} \\ (L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_a e_\beta &= T\rho^{(j)}(\tau_a)_\beta^\mu e_\mu \quad \gamma \text{ incoming} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha = 1, \dots, 2j + 1$.

Note: the coefficients of the transpose representation are the same as the representation, possibly up to a sign.

Specializing to the fundamental representation, i.e. $j = \frac{1}{2}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_a e^A &= -(\tau_a)_B^A e^B \quad \gamma \text{ outgoing} \\ \text{or} \\ (L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_a e_B &= (\tau_a)_B^A e_A \quad \gamma \text{ incoming} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $A = 1, 2$.

On the fundamental representation, with basis $(|+\rangle, |-\rangle)$, the Lie operator acts as

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_x |+\rangle &= -\frac{i}{2} |-\rangle & \tau_y |+\rangle &= \frac{1}{2} |-\rangle & \tau_z |+\rangle &= -\frac{i}{2} |+\rangle & \tau^2 |+\rangle &= -\frac{3}{4} |+\rangle \\ \tau_x |-\rangle &= -\frac{i}{2} |+\rangle & \tau_y |-\rangle &= -\frac{1}{2} |+\rangle & \tau_z |-\rangle &= \frac{i}{2} |-\rangle & \tau^2 |-\rangle &= -\frac{3}{4} |-\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\tau^2 = \vec{\tau} \cdot \vec{\tau}$.

On a generic representation of spin j , we have

$$\tau^2 = -j(j+1)\mathbb{I} \quad (6)$$

The commutator of the Lie operators is

$$[(L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_a, (L_{(\nu', \gamma')})_b] = -\delta_{\nu\nu'} \delta_{\gamma\gamma'} \epsilon_{ab}^c (L_{(\nu, \gamma)})_c \quad (7)$$

We can use the Lie operators to define invariant operators, that is operators which commute with the closure operator $C_{(\nu)}$, refer to equation (2), or with the closure operator of a composite if the Lie operators refer to different nodes, and thus preserve the invariant subspace, i.e. the intertwiners, refer to [9], as

$$D_{(\nu, \gamma; \nu', \gamma')} = \vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu', \gamma')} \quad (8)$$

That allows us to define the following adimensional observables

$$\begin{aligned} D_{(\nu, \gamma)} &= \vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma)} \quad \text{adimensional squared area} \\ D_{(\nu, \gamma; \nu', \gamma')} &= \vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu', \gamma')} \quad \text{dihedral angle} \\ V_{(\nu)}^2 &= \frac{2}{9} [D_{(\nu, \gamma_i \gamma_k)}, D_{(\nu, \gamma_i \gamma_j)}] \quad \text{adimensional squared volume} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $i \neq j \neq k = 1, 2, 3$, independent links in node ν .

Note that

$$V_{(\nu)} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} (D_{(\nu)})^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} D_{(\nu)} &= D_{(\nu, ij k)} = \vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma_i)} \cdot (\vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma_j)} \times \vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma_k)}) = \frac{1}{2} [\vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma_i)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma_k)}, (\vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma_i)} + \vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma_j)})^2] = \\ &= [\vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma_i)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma_k)}, \vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma_i)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu, \gamma_j)}] = [D_{(\nu, \gamma_i \gamma_k)}, D_{(\nu, \gamma_i \gamma_j)}] \\ &\text{unchanged, by definition, under a circular shift of } i, j, k \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

so, last line in equation (9) follows.

Above definitions are justified considering the conjugate momentum p of the Holst Lagrangian L_H , against the connection variable A , which is given up to a constant by the densitized triad E , refer to [3]. The densitized triad is classically a 2-form, of which the flow through a surface measures the surface area, refer to [8]. If we display the momentum in the quantum approach and apply the functional derivative to the link representation, refer to [5], we have

$$\begin{aligned}
p &= \frac{\delta L_H}{\delta A} = \frac{1}{\kappa\gamma_H} E \\
\int_{Surface} E &= \text{Surface area} \\
p &= -i\hbar \frac{\delta}{\delta A} \\
E &= -i\hbar\kappa\gamma_H \frac{\delta}{\delta A} = -i\hbar\kappa\gamma_H \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)}
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

where $\kappa = \frac{8\pi G}{c^3}$, γ_H Holst parameter.

Thus we can define the following operator, refer to [8],

$$\begin{aligned}
(E_{(\gamma)})^2 &= \vec{E}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \cdot \vec{E}_{(\nu,\gamma)} = -(\hbar\kappa\gamma_H)^2 \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} = \\
&= -(\hbar\kappa\gamma_H)^2 \tau^2 = (\hbar\kappa\gamma_H)^2 j(j+1)\mathbb{I}
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Eigenvalues of $(E_{(\gamma)})^2$ are positive, so we can define the area operator

$$A_{(\gamma)} = \sqrt{(E_{(\gamma)})^2} = (\hbar\kappa\gamma_H) \sqrt{j(j+1)}\mathbb{I} = a_0 \sqrt{j(j+1)}\mathbb{I} \tag{14}$$

Note that $a_0 = \hbar\kappa\gamma_H$ has the dimensions of an area, in particular $a_0 = 0.6567\gamma_H \times 10^{-68} m^2$.

Therefore, by associating the a_0 parameter to the Lie operator $\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)}$, we can construct the dimensional squared area and squared volume operators. That is

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{dimensional} \rightarrow \text{dimensional} \\
&\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \rightarrow -ia_0 \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \\
&\text{dimensional squared area} \rightarrow \text{dimensional squared area} \\
&\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \rightarrow -a_0^2 \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \\
&\text{dimensional squared volume} \rightarrow \text{dimensional squared volume} \\
&\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_i)} \cdot (\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_j)} \times \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_k)}) \rightarrow ia_0^3 \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_i)} \cdot (\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_j)} \times \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma_k)})
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

A further comment about the dihedral angle. In order to read the cosine of an angle, we have to normalize it, that is

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{dihedral angle} \rightarrow \text{normalized dihedral angle} \\
D_{(\nu,\gamma;\nu',\gamma')} &\rightarrow \frac{D_{(\nu,\gamma;\nu',\gamma')}}{\sqrt{|\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)}|} \sqrt{|\vec{L}_{(\nu',\gamma')} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu',\gamma')}|}}
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

hence

$$\text{angular measure (radians)} = \arccos\left(\frac{D_{(\nu,\gamma;\nu',\gamma')}}{\sqrt{|\vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu,\gamma)}|} \sqrt{|\vec{L}_{(\nu',\gamma')} \cdot \vec{L}_{(\nu',\gamma')}|}}\right) \quad (17)$$

In the following, if no ambiguity, the angular measure (radians) from a normalized dihedral angle will be stated simply as angle. Note also that the angular measure from a normalized dihedral angle is between the outer normals to the faces of a tetrahedron. The angular measure between the faces is the complement to π radians or to 180° of the former.

2.4 Maximal commuting subalgebra

As for a tetrahedron, possible sets of a maximal commuting subalgebra are:

- $(D_{\nu,ii}, D_{\nu,jj}, D_{\nu,kk}, D_{\nu,hh}, D_{\nu,ij})$ 4 squared areas + 1 dihedral angle
We could think to add also $D_{\nu,kh}$, which is commuting, however it is not linearly independent from the others; in fact $D_{\nu,kh} = -(D_{\nu,ki} + D_{\nu,kj} + D_{\nu,kk})$, that is $(D_{\nu,ki} + D_{\nu,kj}) = -(D_{\nu,kh} + D_{\nu,kk})$, hence $D_{\nu,hh} = D_{\nu,ii} + D_{\nu,jj} - D_{\nu,kk} + 2D_{\nu,ij} - 2D_{\nu,kh}$.
- $(D_{\nu,ii}, D_{\nu,jj}, D_{\nu,kk}, D_{\nu,ij}, D_{\nu,kh})$ 3 squared areas + 2 dihedral angles
We could try to add also the D_ν , that is the squared volume V_ν^2 , which commutes with the squared areas (including $D_{\nu,hh}$), but it does not commute with dihedral angles (including $D_{\nu,ih}$, where i stands for i , or j , or k).
- $(D_{\nu,ii}, D_{\nu,jj}, D_{\nu,kk}, D_{\nu,hh}, V_\nu^2)$ 4 squared areas + 1 squared volume

where $i = \gamma_i$, etc., and $i \neq j \neq k \neq h = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

Therefore, as for a tetrahedron, the maximal commuting subalgebra shows 5 quantum operators against 6 classical degrees of freedom, leaving one geometric property fuzzy.

2.5 Measurements, observables and the uncertainty relation

Referring to [10], here a short recall of the measurement process in quantum mechanics.

Let's define

$$\begin{aligned}
|\alpha\rangle & \text{ quantum state} \\
\langle\alpha|\alpha\rangle & = 1 \quad \text{normalized} \\
A & \text{ observable} \\
A|a\rangle & = a|a\rangle \quad |a\rangle \text{ eigenstate} \quad a \text{ eigenvalue} \\
|a\rangle \langle a|a'\rangle & = \delta_{aa'} \quad \text{orthonormal basis} \\
|\alpha\rangle & = \sum_a c_a |a\rangle \\
c_a & = \langle a|\alpha\rangle \\
\sum_a |c_a|^2 & = 1 \\
\sum_a |a\rangle\langle a| & = \mathbb{I} \quad \text{completeness relation} \\
P_a & = |c_a|^2 = |\langle a|\alpha\rangle|^2 \quad \text{probability for } |\alpha\rangle \text{ to be measured in } |a\rangle \\
\langle A \rangle & = \langle\alpha|A|\alpha\rangle = \sum_a |c_a|^2 a = \sum_a P_a a \quad \text{expectation value}
\end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta A & = A - \langle A \rangle \quad \text{deviation} \\
(\Delta A)^2 & \text{ squared deviation} \\
\langle (\Delta A)^2 \rangle & = \langle A^2 \rangle - \langle A \rangle^2 \quad \text{dispersion, or variance, or mean squared deviation} \\
\sigma_{A,|\alpha\rangle} & = \sqrt{\langle (\Delta A)^2 \rangle} \quad \text{standard deviation}
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Note that if the quantum state $|\alpha\rangle$ is an eigenstate of the observable A , the standard deviation vanishes, i.e. the observable A is sharp.

2.6 Isotropic subspace

Spin networks are invariant states and constitute the isotropic subspace of the product representation. In particular, we are concerned with a 4-valence node. In order to single out a basis of the relative isotropic subspace, as per [6], let's first focus on a 3-valence node and then, building on it, move to a 4-valence node.

2.6.1 3-valence node

Let's consider the product representation $\rho^{(j_1)} \otimes \rho^{(j_2)} \otimes \rho^{(j_3)} : SU(2) \rightarrow V = V_{(j_1)} \otimes V_{(j_2)} \otimes V_{(j_3)} = \mathbb{C}^{(2j_1+1)(2j_2+1)(2j_3+1)}$. Let's assume $j_2 \leq j_3$. The product $\rho^{(j_2)} \otimes \rho^{(j_3)}$ decomposes into a sum of irreducible representations

$$\rho^{(j_1)} \otimes (\rho^{(j_3+j_2)} \oplus \rho^{(j_3+j_2-1)} \oplus \dots \oplus \rho^{(j_3-j_2)}) \tag{20}$$

and it allows an isotropic subspace iff $j_1 = j_3 + j_2 - k_{23}$ for some integer $0 \leq k_{23} \leq 2j_2$.

So, we have

$$\begin{aligned} k_{13} + k_{23} &= 2j_3 \\ k_{21} + k_{31} &= 2j_1 \\ k_{32} + k_{12} &= 2j_2 \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

where $k_{ab} = k_{ba}$. Note the circular shift of 1, 2, 3 as well.

And

$$k_{12} + k_{23} + k_{31} = j_1 + j_2 + j_3 \in \mathbb{N} \tag{22}$$

That means we have 3 threads at the node with $2j_1, 2j_2, 2j_3$ lines, we split each thread as per equation (21) and then we connect k_{ab} lines to the threads a and b .

2.6.2 4-valence node

Let's consider the product representation $\rho^{(j_1)} \otimes \rho^{(j_2)} \otimes \rho^{(j_3)} \otimes \rho^{(j_4)} : SU(2) \rightarrow V = V_{(j_1)} \otimes V_{(j_2)} \otimes V_{(j_3)} \otimes V_{(j_4)} = \mathbb{C}^{(2j_1+1)(2j_2+1)(2j_3+1)(2j_4+1)}$. Let's assume $j_1 \leq j_2$ and $j_3 \leq j_4$. The products $\rho^{(j_2)} \otimes \rho^{(j_1)}$ and $\rho^{(j_4)} \otimes \rho^{(j_3)}$ decompose respectively into the sum of the following irreducible representations

$$(\rho^{(j_2+j_1)} \oplus \rho^{(j_2+j_1-1)} \oplus \dots \oplus \rho^{(j_2-j_1)}) \otimes (\rho^{(j_4+j_3)} \oplus \rho^{(j_4+j_3-1)} \oplus \dots \oplus \rho^{(j_4-j_3)}) \tag{23}$$

and it allows an isotropic subspace iff $j_2 + j_1 - k_{12} = j = j_4 + j_3 - k_{34}$ for two integers $0 \leq k_{12} \leq 2j_1$ and $0 \leq k_{34} \leq 2j_3$. Such conditions list the allowed possibilities, each giving a different isotropic subspace in a direct sum, thus they are independent.

That corresponds to describe algebraically a 4-valence node as two 3-valence nodes with a virtual link j in common. As per the 3-valence case, we can define an intertwiner in each algebraic node, and associate to it the isotropic vector w_{12} and w_{34} respectively. The 4-valence node can be recovered as the tensor product of w_{12} and w_{34} . The procedure can be repeated for any allowed value of j .

3 Fundamental representation $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$

The simplest representation of a tetrahedron is the fundamental one, i.e. $j_1 = j_2 = j_3 = j_4 = \frac{1}{2}$, corresponding to the tensor product $\rho^{(\frac{1}{2})} \otimes \rho^{(\frac{1}{2})} \otimes \rho^{(\frac{1}{2})} \otimes \rho^{(\frac{1}{2})}$. Description in figure 3.

Figure 3: Representation $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$

Expanding the tensor product to irreducible representations, we have

$$\frac{1}{2} \otimes \frac{1}{2} \otimes \frac{1}{2} \otimes \frac{1}{2} = (1 \oplus 0) \otimes (1 \oplus 0) = (2 \oplus 1 \oplus 0) \oplus 1 \oplus 1 \oplus 0 = 2 \oplus 1^3 \oplus 0^2 \quad (24)$$

and so, the isotropic subspace is 2-dimensional.

3.1 A basis of the isotropic subspace

To determine a basis, let's apply what in paragraph 2.6.2 at this representation

$$1 - k_{12} = j = 1 - k_{34} \quad 0 \leq k_{12} \leq 1 \quad 0 \leq k_{34} \leq 1 \quad (25)$$

hence

$$\begin{array}{ccc} k_{12} & j & k_{34} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \end{array} \quad (26)$$

That means

$$\begin{aligned} w_{12,j=1} &= \epsilon^{AE} \epsilon^{BF} e_A \otimes e_B \otimes e_{EF} \\ w_{34,j=1} &= \delta_G^C \delta_H^D e_C \otimes e_D \otimes e^{GH} \\ w_0 &= w_{12,j=1} \otimes w_{34,j=1} \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} w_{12,j=0} &= \epsilon^{AB} e_A \otimes e_B \\ w_{34,j=0} &= \epsilon^{CD} e_C \otimes e_D \\ w_1 &= w_{12,j=0} \otimes w_{34,j=0} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

where $e_{AB} = e_A \odot e_B$, symmetrized tensor product. Note also that the virtual link j is assumed incoming to the algebraic $w_{12,j=1}$ and consequently outgoing from the algebraic $w_{34,j=1}$, thus explaining the dual basis.

So, a basis of the 2-dimensional isotropic subspace is

$$\begin{aligned} w_0 &= \epsilon^{(AC} \epsilon^{BD)} e_A \otimes e_B \otimes e_C \otimes e_D \\ w_1 &= \epsilon^{AB} \epsilon^{CD} e_A \otimes e_B \otimes e_C \otimes e_D \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

where $e^{AB} \otimes e_{CD} = \delta_C^A \delta_D^B$.

However, for computational convenience, let's express the (w_0, w_1) basis against the following elementary vectors

$$\begin{aligned} b &= \epsilon^{AB} \epsilon^{CD} e_A \otimes e_B \otimes e_C \otimes e_D \\ c &= \epsilon^{AC} \epsilon^{BD} e_A \otimes e_B \otimes e_C \otimes e_D \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Here below the graphical description.

Figure 4: b elementary vector

Figure 5: c elementary vector

We have

$$\begin{aligned} w_0 &= -\frac{1}{2}b + c \\ w_1 &= b \end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} b &= w_1 \\ c &= w_0 + \frac{1}{2}w_1 \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

Note: As there are more elementary vectors than the dimension of the isotropic subspace, to get the relation between the elementary vectors or between the (w_0, w_1) basis and the elementary vectors, just write the latter as linear combinations of the former and then use the following identities

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{AB}\epsilon^{AB} &= 2 \\ \epsilon_{AC}\epsilon^{BC} &= \delta_A^B \\ \epsilon_{AB}\epsilon^{CD} &= \delta_A^C\delta_B^D - \delta_B^C\delta_A^D \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

Here below an example.

$$\begin{aligned} c &= a_0w_0 + a_1w_1 \\ \epsilon^{AC}\epsilon^{BD} &= a_0\epsilon^{(AC}\epsilon^{BD)} + a_1\epsilon^{AB}\epsilon^{CD} \\ \epsilon^{AC}\epsilon^{BD} &= \frac{1}{2}a_0\epsilon^{AC}\epsilon^{BD} + \frac{1}{2}a_0\epsilon^{AD}\epsilon^{BC} + a_1\epsilon^{AB}\epsilon^{CD} \\ \delta^{AB}\delta^{CD}(1 - a_0) + \delta^{AD}\delta^{CB}(-1 + a_1 + \frac{1}{2}a_0) + \delta^{AC}\delta^{BD}(-a_1 + \frac{1}{2}a_0) &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

hence

$$a_0 = 1 \quad a_1 = \frac{1}{2}$$

so

$$c = w_0 + \frac{1}{2}w_1$$

For later use, let's compose the elementary vectors

$$\begin{aligned} b^\dagger b &= 4 \\ c^\dagger c &= 4 \\ b^\dagger c &= 2 \end{aligned} \tag{35}$$

Here below a few examples, how they are calculated:

$$\begin{aligned} b^\dagger b &= \epsilon_{AB}\epsilon_{CD}\epsilon^{EF}\epsilon^{GH}e^A \otimes e^B \otimes e^C \otimes e^D \otimes e_E \otimes e_F \otimes e_G \otimes e_H = \\ &= \epsilon_{AB}\epsilon_{CD}\epsilon^{EF}\epsilon^{GH}\delta_E^A\delta_F^B\delta_G^C\delta_H^D = \epsilon_{AB}\epsilon_{CD}\epsilon^{AB}\epsilon^{CD} = \\ &= 2 \cdot 2 = 4 \end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
b^\dagger c &= \epsilon_{AB}\epsilon_{CD}\epsilon^{EG}\epsilon^{FH}e^A \otimes e^B \otimes e^C \otimes e^D \otimes e_E \otimes e_F \otimes e_G \otimes e_H = \\
&= \epsilon_{AB}\epsilon_{CD}\epsilon^{EG}\epsilon^{FH}\delta_E^A\delta_F^B\delta_G^C\delta_H^D = \epsilon_{AB}\epsilon_{CD}\epsilon^{AC}\epsilon^{BD} = \\
&= \delta_B^C\delta_C^B = \delta_B^B = 2
\end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

Using equations (31) and (35), we can compose the (w_o, w_1) basis

$$\begin{aligned}
w_0^\dagger w_0 &= 3 \\
w_1^\dagger w_1 &= 4 \\
w_0^\dagger w_1 &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

hence, the (w_o, w_1) basis is orthogonal.

3.2 Operators acting on the elementary vectors

The invariant operators act on the elementary vectors as

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12}b &= \frac{3}{4}b \\
D_{12}c &= \frac{1}{2}b - \frac{1}{4}c
\end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{13}b &= -\frac{1}{4}b + \frac{1}{2}c \\
D_{13}c &= \frac{3}{4}c
\end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{14}b &= \frac{1}{4}b - \frac{1}{2}c \\
D_{14}c &= -\frac{1}{2}b + \frac{1}{4}c
\end{aligned} \tag{41}$$

Here below, as an example, how the action of the operator D_{12} is calculated. To

simplify the notation, let's define $e_A \otimes e_B \otimes e_C \otimes e_D = |ABCD\rangle$.

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12}b &= \vec{L}_1 \cdot \vec{L}_2 \epsilon^{AB} \epsilon^{CD} |ABCD\rangle = \\
&= \epsilon^{AB} \epsilon^{CD} (|(\tau_x A)(\tau_x B)CD\rangle + \\
&+ |(\tau_y A)(\tau_y B)CD\rangle + \\
&+ |(\tau_z A)(\tau_z B)CD\rangle) = \\
&= \frac{1}{4} \epsilon^{AB} \epsilon^{CD} ((-1)|BACD\rangle + \\
&+ (-1)|BACD\rangle + \\
&+ |ABCD\rangle) = \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (-2 \epsilon^{AB} \epsilon^{CD} (-1)|ABCD\rangle + \\
&+ \epsilon^{AB} \epsilon^{CD} |ABCD\rangle) = \\
&= \frac{3}{4} \epsilon^{AB} \epsilon^{CD} |ABCD\rangle = \\
&= \frac{3}{4} b
\end{aligned} \tag{42}$$

Note: $\epsilon^{AB} \Rightarrow A \neq B$, hence the action of the τ 's, refer to equation (5), is consequent. Moreover the relabeling $A \rightleftharpoons B$ gives $\epsilon^{BA} = -\epsilon^{AB}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12}c &= \vec{L}_1 \cdot \vec{L}_2 \epsilon^{AC} \epsilon^{BD} |ABCD\rangle = \\
&= \epsilon^{AC} \epsilon^{BD} (|(\tau_x A)(\tau_x B)CD\rangle + \\
&\quad + |(\tau_y A)(\tau_y B)CD\rangle + \\
&\quad + |(\tau_z A)(\tau_z B)CD\rangle) = \\
&= \epsilon^{AC} \epsilon^{BD} \frac{1}{4} ((-1)|CDCD\rangle \delta_{AB \text{ no sum}} + \\
&\quad + (-1)|BACD\rangle (1 - \delta_{AB \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&\quad + |CDCD\rangle \delta_{AB \text{ no sum}} + \\
&\quad + (-1)|BACD\rangle (1 - \delta_{AB \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&\quad + (-1)|ABCD\rangle \delta_{AB \text{ no sum}} + \\
&\quad + |ABCD\rangle (1 - \delta_{AB \text{ no sum}})) = \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (\text{blank} + \\
&\quad + \epsilon^{AD} \epsilon^{BC} (-1)|ABCD\rangle (1 - \delta_{AB \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&\quad + \text{blank} + \\
&\quad + \epsilon^{AD} \epsilon^{BC} (-1)|ABCD\rangle (1 - \delta_{AB \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&\quad + \epsilon^{AC} \epsilon^{BD} (-1)|ABCD\rangle \delta_{AB \text{ no sum}} + \\
&\quad + \epsilon^{AC} \epsilon^{BD} |ABCD\rangle (1 - \delta_{AB \text{ no sum}})) = \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (2\epsilon^{AD} \epsilon^{BC} (-1)|ABCD\rangle + \epsilon^{AC} \epsilon^{BD} |ABCD\rangle) = \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (-2(c-b) + c) = \\
&= \frac{1}{2}b - \frac{1}{4}c
\end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

Note: The action of the τ 's splits each line in two lines whether the acted indices are equal, $\Rightarrow \delta_{AB \text{ no sum}}$, or not equal, $\Rightarrow (1 - \delta_{AB \text{ no sum}})$. The first and third line cancel each other (a *blank* is posted for an easy reading). The relabeling $A \rightleftharpoons B$ recovers the initial tensor product in the second and fourth line. The terms with the constraint on the indices cancel one another, due to the opposite sign and because $\epsilon^{AD} \epsilon^{BC} \delta_{AB \text{ no sum}} = \epsilon^{AC} \epsilon^{BD} \delta_{AB \text{ no sum}}$.

3.3 Operators acting on the (w_0, w_1) basis

Considering equations (31), (32), (39), (40), (41), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12}w_0 &= -\frac{1}{4}w_0 \\
D_{12}w_1 &= \frac{3}{4}w_1
\end{aligned} \tag{44}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{13}w_0 &= \frac{1}{2}w_0 + \frac{3}{8}w_1 \\
D_{13}w_1 &= \frac{1}{2}w_0
\end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{14}w_0 &= \frac{1}{2}w_0 - \frac{3}{8}w_1 \\
D_{14}w_1 &= -\frac{1}{2}w_0
\end{aligned}
\tag{46}$$

Note that the D_{12} operator is diagonal on the (w_0, w_1) basis.

As for the squared areas, considering equation (6) or, specifically for the $j = \frac{1}{2}$ spin, equation (5), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11}w_0 &= -\frac{3}{4}w_0 \\
D_{11}w_1 &= -\frac{3}{4}w_1
\end{aligned}
\tag{47}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{22}w_0 &= -\frac{3}{4}w_0 \\
D_{22}w_1 &= -\frac{3}{4}w_1
\end{aligned}
\tag{48}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{33}w_0 &= -\frac{3}{4}w_0 \\
D_{33}w_1 &= -\frac{3}{4}w_1
\end{aligned}
\tag{49}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{44}w_0 &= -\frac{3}{4}w_0 \\
D_{44}w_1 &= -\frac{3}{4}w_1
\end{aligned}
\tag{50}$$

As per equation (9), the squared volume operator is defined as $V^2 = \frac{2}{9}[D_{13}, D_{12}]$. Considering equations (44), (45), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
V^2w_0 &= -\frac{1}{12}w_1 \\
V^2w_1 &= \frac{1}{9}w_0
\end{aligned}
\tag{51}$$

3.4 Maximal commuting subalgebra $(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{33}, D_{44}, D_{12})$ on the (w_0, w_1) basis

On the (w_0, w_1) basis, the maximal commuting subalgebra shows as $(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{33}, D_{44}, D_{12})$. Here below the observables on the respective basis elements.

3.4.1 Observables on the w_0 basis element

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11,w_0} &= -\frac{3}{4} \text{ sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{11,w_0} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \text{ sharp} \\
D_{22,w_0} &= -\frac{3}{4} \text{ sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{22,w_0} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \text{ sharp} \\
D_{33,w_0} &= -\frac{3}{4} \text{ sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{33,w_0} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \text{ sharp} \\
D_{44,w_0} &= -\frac{3}{4} \text{ sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{44,w_0} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \text{ sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{52}$$

Here below an example how the squared area is calculated.

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{11} \rangle_{w_0} &= \frac{w_0^\dagger D_{11} w_0}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = -\frac{3}{4} \frac{w_0^\dagger w_0}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = -\frac{3}{4} \\
\sigma_{D_{11},w_0} &= 0 \quad w_0 \text{ is an eigenstate of } D_{11}
\end{aligned} \tag{53}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12,w_0} &= -\frac{1}{4} \text{ sharp} \\
\text{normalized } D_{12,w_0} &= -\frac{1}{3} \text{ sharp} \\
\text{angle}_{12,w_0} &= 109.5^\circ \text{ sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{54}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{w_0} &= \frac{1}{2} \text{ expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{w_0} &= \frac{2}{3} \text{ expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{13} \rangle_{w_0} &= 48.2^\circ \text{ expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{13},w_0} &= \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13},w_0} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \approx 0.577 \\
\frac{2}{3} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{13,w_0} \leq \frac{2}{3} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \text{ fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{13,w_0} \leq 84.9^\circ \text{ fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{55}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{w_0} &= \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{14} \rangle_{w_0} &= \frac{2}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{14} \rangle_{w_0} &= 48.2^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{14}, w_0} &= \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{14}, w_0} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \approx 0.577 \\
\frac{2}{3} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{14, w_0} \leq \frac{2}{3} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{14, w_0} \leq 84.9^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{56}$$

Here below an example how the dihedral angle is calculated.

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{w_0} &= \frac{w_0^\dagger D_{13} w_0}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = \frac{w_0^\dagger (\frac{1}{2} w_0 + \frac{3}{8} w_1)}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = \frac{(\frac{1}{2} w_0^\dagger w_0 + \frac{3}{8} w_0^\dagger w_1)}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \frac{w_0^\dagger w_0}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = \frac{1}{2} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{w_0} &= \frac{\langle D_{13} \rangle_{w_0}}{\sqrt{|D_{11, w_0}|} \sqrt{|D_{33, w_0}|}} = \frac{\frac{1}{2}}{\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}} = \frac{2}{3} \\
\langle D_{13}^2 \rangle_{w_0} &= \frac{w_0^\dagger D_{13}^2 w_0}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = \frac{w_0^\dagger D_{13} (\frac{1}{2} w_0 + \frac{3}{8} w_1)}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = \\
&= \frac{w_0^\dagger (\frac{1}{2} (\frac{1}{2} w_0 + \frac{3}{8} w_1) + \frac{3}{8} (\frac{1}{2} w_0))}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = \frac{(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{3}{16}) w_0^\dagger w_0}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = \frac{7}{16} \\
\langle (\Delta D_{13})^2 \rangle_{w_0} &= \langle D_{13}^2 \rangle_{w_0} - \langle D_{13} \rangle_{w_0}^2 = \frac{7}{16} - \frac{1}{4} = \frac{3}{16} \\
\sigma_{D_{13}, w_0} &= \sqrt{\langle (\Delta D_{13})^2 \rangle_{w_0}} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13}, w_0} &= \frac{\frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}}{\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}} \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}
\end{aligned} \tag{57}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle V^2 \rangle_{w_0} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{dimensional } \langle V^2 \rangle_{w_0} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{V^2, w_0} &= \frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}} \\
\text{dimensional } \sigma_{V^2, w_0} &= -\frac{1}{6\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 \quad (58) \\
-\frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}} &\leq V_{w_0}^2 \leq \frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
-\frac{1}{6\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 &\leq \text{dimensional } V_{w_0}^2 \leq \frac{1}{6\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned}$$

Here below an example how the squared volume is calculated.

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle V^2 \rangle_{w_0} &= \frac{w_0^\dagger V^2 w_0}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = \frac{w_0^\dagger (-\frac{1}{12} w_1)}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = \frac{(-\frac{1}{12} w_0^\dagger w_1)}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = 0 \\
\langle (V^2)^2 \rangle_{w_0} &= \frac{w_0^\dagger (V^2)^2 w_0}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = \frac{w_0^\dagger V^2 (-\frac{1}{12} w_1)}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = \frac{w_0^\dagger (-\frac{1}{12} (\frac{1}{9} w_0))}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = \\
&= -\frac{1}{108} \frac{w_0^\dagger w_0}{w_0^\dagger w_0} = -\frac{1}{108} \quad (59) \\
\langle (\Delta V^2)^2 \rangle_{w_0} &= \langle (V^2)^2 \rangle_{w_0} - \langle V^2 \rangle_{w_0}^2 = -\frac{1}{108} \\
\sigma_{V^2, w_0} &= \sqrt{\langle (\Delta V^2)^2 \rangle_{w_0}} = \frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}}
\end{aligned}$$

A remark about the +ve/-ve dimensional squared volume. As per classical geometry, a tetrahedron reflected against a plane, singled out by a face, shows the same squared areas and the same dihedral angles as the original one, but a squared volume opposite in sign. The latter if the squared volume is calculated as the mixed product of the outer normals to the faces. A reflection can not be obtained by a rotation, therefore a tetrahedron and its reflection against a face are two different geometric objects. For more details, refer to appendix A.1.

3.4.2 Observables on the w_1 basis element

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11,w_1} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{11,w_1} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{22,w_1} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{22,w_1} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{33,w_1} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{33,w_1} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{44,w_1} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{44,w_1} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{60}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12,w_1} &= \frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{normalized } D_{12,w_1} &= 1 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{angle}_{12,w_1} &= 0^\circ \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{61}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{w_1} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{w_1} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{13} \rangle_{w_1} &= 90^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{13},w_1} &= \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13},w_1} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \approx 0.577 \\
-\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{13,w_1} \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
54.7^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{13,w_1} \leq 125.3^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{62}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{w_1} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{14} \rangle_{w_1} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{14} \rangle_{w_1} &= 90^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{14}, w_1} &= \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{14}, w_1} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \approx 0.577 \\
-\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{14, w_1} \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
54.7^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{14, w_1} \leq 125.3^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{63}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle V^2 \rangle_{w_1} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{dimensional } \langle V^2 \rangle_{w_1} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{V^2, w_1} &= \frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}} \\
\text{dimensional } \sigma_{V^2, w_1} &= -\frac{1}{6\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 \\
-\frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}} &\leq V_{w_1}^2 \leq \frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
-\frac{1}{6\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 &\leq \text{dimensional } V_{w_1}^2 \leq \frac{1}{6\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{64}$$

Note that the angle_{12, w_1} measures 0° sharp. That would cause a classical tetrahedron to be flat, however the non commutativity of the other observables allows a quantum tetrahedron not to vanish.

As for the +ve/-ve dimensional squared volume, refer to the remark at the end of paragraph 3.4.1.

3.5 Maximal commuting subalgebra $(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{33}, D_{44}, V^2)$ on the (e_1, e_2) basis

Let's diagonalize the squared volume operator V^2 . Working on the (w_0, w_1) basis and looking for the eigenvalues λ and eigenstates e , solutions to $V^2 e = \lambda e$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\lambda_1 &= \frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}} \\
\lambda_2 &= -\frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}} \\
e_1 &= -\frac{2i}{\sqrt{3}} w_0 + w_1 \\
e_2 &= \frac{2i}{\sqrt{3}} w_0 + w_1
\end{aligned} \tag{65}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} w_0 &= \frac{\sqrt{3}i}{4}(e_1 - e_2) \\ w_1 &= \frac{1}{2}(e_1 + e_2) \end{aligned} \tag{66}$$

also

$$\begin{aligned} e_1^\dagger e_1 &= 8 \\ e_2^\dagger e_2 &= 8 \\ e_1^\dagger e_2 &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{67}$$

hence, the (e_1, e_2) basis is orthogonal.

On the (e_1, e_2) basis, the maximal commuting subalgebra shows as $(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{33}, D_{44}, V^2)$.

3.5.1 Operators acting on the (e_1, e_2) basis

$$\begin{aligned} D_{12}e_1 &= \frac{1}{4}e_1 + \frac{1}{2}e_2 \\ D_{12}e_2 &= \frac{1}{2}e_1 + \frac{1}{4}e_2 \end{aligned} \tag{68}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{13}e_1 &= \frac{1}{4}e_1 - \frac{1}{4}(1 + \sqrt{3}i)e_2 \\ D_{13}e_2 &= -\frac{1}{4}(1 - \sqrt{3}i)e_1 + \frac{1}{4}e_2 \end{aligned} \tag{69}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{14}e_1 &= \frac{1}{4}e_1 - \frac{1}{4}(1 - \sqrt{3}i)e_2 \\ D_{14}e_2 &= -\frac{1}{4}(1 + \sqrt{3}i)e_1 + \frac{1}{4}e_2 \end{aligned} \tag{70}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{11}e_1 &= -\frac{3}{4}e_1 \\ D_{11}e_2 &= -\frac{3}{4}e_2 \end{aligned} \tag{71}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{22}e_1 &= -\frac{3}{4}e_1 \\ D_{22}e_2 &= -\frac{3}{4}e_2 \end{aligned} \tag{72}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{33}e_1 &= -\frac{3}{4}e_1 \\ D_{33}e_2 &= -\frac{3}{4}e_2 \end{aligned} \tag{73}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{44}e_1 &= -\frac{3}{4}e_1 \\
D_{44}e_2 &= -\frac{3}{4}e_2
\end{aligned} \tag{74}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
V^2e_1 &= \frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}}e_1 \\
V^2e_2 &= -\frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}}e_2
\end{aligned} \tag{75}$$

Here below the observables on the respective basis elements.

3.5.2 Observables on the e_1 basis element

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11,e_1} &= -\frac{3}{4} \text{ sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{11,e_1} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \text{ sharp} \\
D_{22,e_1} &= -\frac{3}{4} \text{ sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{22,e_1} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \text{ sharp} \\
D_{33,e_1} &= -\frac{3}{4} \text{ sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{33,e_1} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \text{ sharp} \\
D_{44,e_1} &= -\frac{3}{4} \text{ sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{44,e_1} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \text{ sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{76}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{12} \rangle_{e_1} &= \frac{1}{4} \text{ expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{12} \rangle_{e_1} &= \frac{1}{3} \text{ expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{12} \rangle_{e_1} &= 70.5^\circ \text{ expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{12},e_1} &= \frac{1}{2} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{12},e_1} &= \frac{2}{3} \approx 0.667 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{2}{3} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{12,e_1} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \text{ fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{12,e_1} \leq 109.5^\circ \text{ fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{77}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{e_1} &= \frac{1}{4} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{e_1} &= \frac{1}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{13} \rangle_{e_1} &= 70.5^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{13}, e_1} &= \frac{1}{2} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13}, e_1} &= \frac{2}{3} \approx 0.667 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{2}{3} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{13, e_1} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{13, e_1} \leq 109.5^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{78}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{e_1} &= \frac{1}{4} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{14} \rangle_{e_1} &= \frac{1}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{14} \rangle_{e_1} &= 70.5^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{14}, e_1} &= \frac{1}{2} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{14}, e_1} &= \frac{2}{3} \approx 0.667 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{2}{3} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{14, e_1} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{14, e_1} \leq 109.5^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{79}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{e_1}^2 &= \frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } V_{e_1}^2 &= -\frac{1}{6\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{80}$$

3.5.3 Observables on the e_2 basis element

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11,e_2} &= -\frac{3}{4} \text{ sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{11,e_2} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \text{ sharp} \\
D_{22,e_2} &= -\frac{3}{4} \text{ sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{22,e_2} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \text{ sharp} \\
D_{33,e_2} &= -\frac{3}{4} \text{ sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{33,e_2} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \text{ sharp} \\
D_{44,e_2} &= -\frac{3}{4} \text{ sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{44,e_2} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \text{ sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{81}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{12} \rangle_{e_2} &= \frac{1}{4} \text{ expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{12} \rangle_{e_2} &= \frac{1}{3} \text{ expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{12} \rangle_{e_2} &= 70.5^\circ \text{ expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{12},e_2} &= \frac{1}{2} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{12},e_2} &= \frac{2}{3} \approx 0.667 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{2}{3} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{12,e_2} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \text{ fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{12,e_2} \leq 109.5^\circ \text{ fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{82}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{e_2} &= \frac{1}{4} \text{ expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{e_2} &= \frac{1}{3} \text{ expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{13} \rangle_{e_2} &= 70.5^\circ \text{ expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{13},e_2} &= \frac{1}{2} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13},e_2} &= \frac{2}{3} \approx 0.667 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{2}{3} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{13,e_2} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \text{ fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{13,e_2} \leq 109.5^\circ \text{ fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{83}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{e_2} &= \frac{1}{4} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{14} \rangle_{e_2} &= \frac{1}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{14} \rangle_{e_2} &= 70.5^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{14}, e_2} &= \frac{1}{2} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{14}, e_2} &= \frac{2}{3} \approx 0.667 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{2}{3} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{14, e_2} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{14, e_2} \leq 109.5^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{84}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{e_2}^2 &= -\frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } V_{e_2}^2 &= \frac{1}{6\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{85}$$

As for the +ve/-ve dimensional squared volume, on the e_2/e_1 basis elements respectively, refer to the remark at the end of paragraph 3.4.1.

3.6 A general spin network in the representation $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$

Any spin network sn can be written as a linear combination of the elements of a basis. For instance, let's normalize the (w_0, w_1) basis

$$\begin{aligned}
w'_0 &= \frac{w_0}{\sqrt{w_0^\dagger w_0}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} w_0 \\
w'_1 &= \frac{w_1}{\sqrt{w_1^\dagger w_1}} = \frac{1}{2} w_1
\end{aligned} \tag{86}$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned}
w_0'^\dagger w'_0 &= 1 \\
w_1'^\dagger w'_1 &= 1 \\
w_0'^\dagger w'_1 &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{87}$$

i.e. (w'_0, w'_1) is an orthonormal basis.

Here below how the operators act on the (w'_0, w'_1) basis.

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12} w'_0 &= -\frac{1}{4} w'_0 \\
D_{12} w'_1 &= \frac{3}{4} w'_1
\end{aligned} \tag{88}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{13}w'_0 &= \frac{1}{2}w'_0 + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}w'_1 \\
D_{13}w'_1 &= \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}w'_0
\end{aligned} \tag{89}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{14}w'_0 &= \frac{1}{2}w'_0 - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}w'_1 \\
D_{14}w'_1 &= -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}w'_0
\end{aligned} \tag{90}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
V^2w'_0 &= -\frac{1}{6\sqrt{3}}w'_1 \\
V^2w'_1 &= \frac{1}{6\sqrt{3}}w'_0
\end{aligned} \tag{91}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
sn &= c_0w'_0 + c_1w'_1 \\
sn^\dagger sn &= 1 \quad \textit{normalization} \\
|c_0|^2 + |c_1|^2 &= 1 \\
|c_0|^2 &= \cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \\
|c_1|^2 &= \sin^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \\
c_0 &= \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \\
c_1 &= \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)e^{i\phi} \\
c_0^\dagger c_1 + c_1^\dagger c_0 &= 2\cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)\sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)\cos(\phi) = \sin(\theta)\cos(\phi)
\end{aligned} \tag{92}$$

The coefficients, c_0 and c_1 , are set considering that a quantum state is defined up to a common phase factor. So, each tetrahedron is a qubit, parameterized by (θ, ϕ) . Refer to [10], from which I kept the $\frac{\theta}{2}$ argument to be formally in accord. Note that $sn(\theta = 0) = w'_0$ and $sn(\theta = \pi) = w'_1$ (in this latter, showing only one term, the phase factor is unessential).

Here below the observables of the general spin network.

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11,sn} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{22,sn} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{33,sn} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{44,sn} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\langle D_{12} \rangle_{sn} &= -\frac{1}{4} + \sin^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \\
\sigma_{D_{12},sn} &= \left| \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \right| \\
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{sn} &= \frac{1}{2} \cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} \sin(\theta) \cos(\phi) \\
\sigma_{D_{13},sn} &= \sqrt{-\left(\frac{1}{2} \cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} \sin(\theta) \cos(\phi) - \frac{1}{4}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{4}} \\
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{sn} &= \frac{1}{2} \cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} \sin(\theta) \cos(\phi) \\
\sigma_{D_{14},sn} &= \sqrt{-\left(\frac{1}{2} \cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} \sin(\theta) \cos(\phi) - \frac{1}{4}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{4}} \\
\langle V^2 \rangle_{sn} &= \frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}} \sin(\theta) \sin(\phi) \\
\sigma_{V^2,sn} &= \frac{i}{6\sqrt{3}} \sqrt{1 - \sin^2(\theta) \sin^2(\phi)}
\end{aligned} \tag{93}$$

4 Representation $(1, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 1)$

Let's move to a higher spin representation, e.g. $j_1 = 1, j_2 = \frac{1}{2}, j_3 = \frac{1}{2}, j_4 = 1$, corresponding to the tensor product $\rho^{(1)} \otimes \rho^{(\frac{1}{2})} \otimes \rho^{(\frac{1}{2})} \otimes \rho^{(1)}$. Description in figure 6.

Figure 6: Representation $(1, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 1)$

Expanding the tensor product to irreducible representations, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
1 \otimes \frac{1}{2} \otimes \frac{1}{2} \otimes 1 &= \left(\frac{3}{2} \oplus \frac{1}{2}\right) \otimes \left(\frac{3}{2} \oplus \frac{1}{2}\right) = \\
&= (3 \oplus 2 \oplus 1 \oplus 0) \oplus (2 \oplus 1) \oplus (2 \oplus 1) \oplus (1 \oplus 0) = \\
&= 3 \oplus 2^3 \oplus 1^4 \oplus 0^2
\end{aligned} \tag{94}$$

and so, the isotropic subspace is 2-dimensional.

4.1 A basis of the isotropic subspace

To determine a basis, let's apply what in paragraph 2.6.2 at this representation

$$\frac{3}{2} - k_{12} = j = \frac{3}{2} - k_{34} \quad 0 \leq k_{12} \leq 1 \quad 0 \leq k_{34} \leq 1 \tag{95}$$

hence

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
k_{12} & j & k_{34} \\
0 & \frac{3}{2} & 0 \\
1 & \frac{1}{2} & 1
\end{array} \tag{96}$$

That means

$$\begin{aligned}
w_{12, j=\frac{3}{2}} &= \epsilon^{A_1 E_1} \epsilon^{A_2 E_2} \epsilon^{B E_3} e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_B \otimes e_{E_1 E_2 E_3} \\
w_{34, j=\frac{3}{2}} &= \delta_{F_1}^{D_1} \delta_{F_2}^{D_2} \delta_{F_3}^C e^{F_1 F_2 F_3} \otimes e_C \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \\
v_0 &= w_{12, j=\frac{3}{2}} \otimes w_{34, j=\frac{3}{2}}
\end{aligned} \tag{97}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
w_{12, j=\frac{1}{2}} &= \epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{A_2 E} e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_B \otimes e_E \\
w_{34, j=\frac{1}{2}} &= \delta_F^{D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} e^F \otimes e_C \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \\
v_1 &= w_{12, j=\frac{1}{2}} \otimes w_{34, j=\frac{1}{2}}
\end{aligned} \tag{98}$$

where $e_{AB} = e_A \odot e_B$ and $e_{ABC} = e_A \odot e_B \odot e_C$, symmetrized tensor product. Note also that the virtual link j is assumed incoming to the algebraic $w_{12,j}$ and consequently outgoing from the algebraic $w_{34,j}$, thus explaining the dual basis.

So, a basis of the 2-dimensional isotropic subspace is

$$\begin{aligned} v_0 &= \epsilon^{(A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{BC)} e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_B \otimes e_C \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \\ v_1 &= \epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_B \otimes e_C \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \end{aligned} \quad (99)$$

where $e^{ABC} \otimes e_{DEF} = \delta_D^A \delta_E^B \delta_F^C$.

However, for computational convenience, let's express the (v_0, v_1) basis against the following elementary vectors

$$\begin{aligned} r &= \epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_B \otimes e_C \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \\ s &= \epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{BC} e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_B \otimes e_C \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \end{aligned} \quad (100)$$

Here below the graphical description.

Figure 7: r elementary vector

Figure 8: s elementary vector

We have

$$\begin{aligned} v_0 &= -\frac{2}{3}r + s \\ v_1 &= r \end{aligned} \tag{101}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} r &= v_1 \\ s &= v_0 + \frac{2}{3}v_1 \end{aligned} \tag{102}$$

Note: As there are more elementary vectors than the dimension of the isotropic subspace, to get the relation between the elementary vectors or between the (v_0, v_1) basis and the elementary vectors, just write the latter as linear combinations of the former and then use the identities in equation (33).

For later use, let's compose the elementary vectors

$$\begin{aligned} r^\dagger r &= \frac{9}{2} \\ s^\dagger s &= 6 \\ r^\dagger s &= 3 \end{aligned} \tag{103}$$

Here below a few examples, how they are calculated:

$$\begin{aligned} r^\dagger r &= \epsilon_{A_1 B} \epsilon_{A_2 D_1} \epsilon_{D_2 C} \epsilon^{E_1 F} \epsilon^{E_2 H_1} \epsilon^{H_2 G} e^{A_1 A_2} \otimes e^B \otimes e^C \otimes e^{D_1 D_2} \otimes \\ &\otimes e_{E_1 E_2} \otimes e_F \otimes e_G \otimes e_{H_1 H_2} = \\ &= \epsilon_{(A_1 B} \epsilon_{A_2 D_1)} \epsilon_{D_2 C} \epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{(A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C)} = \\ &= \frac{1}{4} (\epsilon_{A_1 B} \epsilon_{A_2 D_1} \epsilon_{D_2 C} + \epsilon_{A_1 D_1} \epsilon_{A_2 B} \epsilon_{D_2 C}) \times \\ &\times (\epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} + \epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{C D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 A_2}) = \\ &= \frac{1}{4} (2 \times 2 \times 2 + 2 \times 2 + 2 \times 2 + 2) = \frac{9}{2} \end{aligned} \tag{104}$$

$$\begin{aligned} r^\dagger s &= \epsilon_{A_1 B} \epsilon_{A_2 D_1} \epsilon_{D_2 C} \epsilon^{E_1 H_1} \epsilon^{E_2 H_2} \epsilon^{F G} e^{A_1 A_2} \otimes e^B \otimes e^C \otimes e^{D_1 D_2} \otimes \\ &\otimes e_{E_1 E_2} \otimes e_F \otimes e_G \otimes e_{H_1 H_2} = \\ &= \epsilon_{A_1 B} \epsilon_{A_2 D_1} \epsilon_{D_2 C} \epsilon^{(A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2)} \epsilon^{BC} = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{A_1 B} \epsilon_{A_2 D_1} \epsilon_{D_2 C} (\epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{BC} + \epsilon^{A_1 D_2} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{BC}) = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} (2 + 2 \times 2) = 3 \end{aligned} \tag{105}$$

Using equations (101) and (103), we can compose the (v_0, v_1) basis

$$\begin{aligned} v_0^\dagger v_0 &= 4 \\ v_1^\dagger v_1 &= \frac{9}{2} \\ v_0^\dagger v_1 &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{106}$$

hence, the (v_0, v_1) basis is orthogonal.

4.2 Operators acting on the elementary vectors

The invariant operators act on the elementary vectors as

$$\begin{aligned} D_{12}r &= r \\ D_{12}s &= r - \frac{1}{2}s \end{aligned} \tag{107}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{13}r &= -\frac{1}{2}s \\ D_{13}s &= -r + \frac{1}{2}s \end{aligned} \tag{108}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{14}r &= r + \frac{1}{2}s \\ D_{14}s &= 2s \end{aligned} \tag{109}$$

Here below, as an example, how the action of the operator D_{12} is calculated. To simplify the notation, let's define $e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_B \otimes e_C \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} = |(A_1 A_2)BC(D_1 D_2)\rangle$.

$$\begin{aligned} D_{12}r &= \vec{L}_1 \cdot \vec{L}_2 \epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} |(A_1 A_2)BC(D_1 D_2)\rangle = \\ &= \epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} (|((\tau_x A_1) A_2)(\tau_x B)C(D_1 D_2)\rangle + |(A_1(\tau_x A_2))(\tau_x B)C(D_1 D_2)\rangle) + \\ &+ |((\tau_y A_1) A_2)(\tau_y B)C(D_1 D_2)\rangle + |(A_1(\tau_y A_2))(\tau_y B)C(D_1 D_2)\rangle + \\ &+ |((\tau_z A_1) A_2)(\tau_z B)C(D_1 D_2)\rangle + |(A_1(\tau_z A_2))(\tau_z B)C(D_1 D_2)\rangle) = \\ &= \epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} \frac{1}{4} (\text{blank} + (-1)|(\overline{A_1 D_1}) A_1 C(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}} + \\ &+ (-1)|(BA_2) A_1 C(D_1 D_2)\rangle + (-1)|(A_1 B) A_2 C(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}}) + \\ &+ \text{blank} + |(A_1 D_1) A_1 C(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}} + \\ &+ (-1)|(BA_2) A_1 C(D_1 D_2)\rangle + (-1)|(A_1 B) A_2 C(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}}) + \\ &+ \text{blank} + (-1)|(\overline{A_1 A_2}) BC(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}} + \\ &+ |(A_1 A_2) BC(D_1 D_2)\rangle + |(A_1 A_2) BC(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}})) = \\ &= \frac{1}{4} (\text{blank} + \text{blank} + \\ &- (-1) \epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} + (-1) \epsilon^{A_1 A_2} \epsilon^{B D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} (1 - \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}}) + \\ &+ \text{blank} + \text{blank} + \\ &- (-1) \epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} + (-1) \epsilon^{A_1 A_2} \epsilon^{B D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} (1 - \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}}) + \\ &+ \text{blank} + (-1) \epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}} + \\ &+ \epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} + \epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} (1 - \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}})) |(A_1 A_2) BC(D_1 D_2)\rangle = \\ &= \frac{1}{4} (4r) = r \end{aligned} \tag{110}$$

Note: The action of the τ 's splits each line in two lines whether the acted indices are equal, $\Rightarrow \delta_{A_1 B \text{ no sum}}$, $\Rightarrow \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}}$, or not equal, $\Rightarrow (1 - \delta_{A_1 B \text{ no sum}})$, \Rightarrow

$(1 - \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}})$. However $\epsilon^{A_1 B} \Rightarrow A_1 \neq B$ (a *blank* is posted for an easy reading). The action of the τ 's, refer to equation (5), is consequent. What remaining in the first and third line cancel each other (a *blank* is posted for an easy reading). The relabeling $A_1 \equiv B$, in the second and fourth line, recovers the initial epsilon product, with $\epsilon^{BA_1} = -\epsilon^{A_1 B}$. The relabeling $A_2 \equiv B$, in the second and fourth line, gives an $\epsilon^{A_1 A_2}$, antisymmetric in $[A_1 A_2]$, which vanishes when composed with the basis $|(A_1 A_2)\rangle$, symmetric in $(A_1 A_2)$. The terms with the constraint on the indices cancel one another, due to the opposite sign and because $\epsilon^{A_1 A_2} \epsilon^{BD_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}} = \epsilon^{A_1 B} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{D_2 C} \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12}s &= \vec{L}_1 \cdot \vec{L}_2 \epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{BC} |(A_1 A_2)BC(D_1 D_2)\rangle = \\
&= \epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{BC} (|((\tau_x A_1) A_2)(\tau_x B)C(D_1 D_2)\rangle + |(A_1(\tau_x A_2))(\tau_x B)C(D_1 D_2)\rangle + \\
&+ |((\tau_y A_1) A_2)(\tau_y B)C(D_1 D_2)\rangle + |(A_1(\tau_y A_2))(\tau_y B)C(D_1 D_2)\rangle + \\
&+ |((\tau_z A_1) A_2)(\tau_z B)C(D_1 D_2)\rangle + |(A_1(\tau_z A_2))(\tau_z B)C(D_1 D_2)\rangle) = \\
&= \epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{BC} \frac{1}{4} ((-1)|(D_1 A_2)CC(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_1 B \text{ no sum}} + (-1)|(A_1 D_2)CC(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}} + \\
&+ (-1)|(BA_2)A_1C(D_1 D_2)\rangle(1 - \delta_{A_1 B \text{ no sum}}) + (-1)|(A_1 B)A_2C(D_1 D_2)\rangle(1 - \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&+ |(D_1 A_2)CC(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_1 B \text{ no sum}} + |(A_1 D_2)CC(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}} + \\
&+ (-1)|(BA_2)A_1C(D_1 D_2)\rangle(1 - \delta_{A_1 B \text{ no sum}}) + (-1)|(A_1 B)A_2C(D_1 D_2)\rangle(1 - \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&+ (-1)|(A_1 A_2)BC(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_1 B \text{ no sum}} + (-1)|(A_1 A_2)BC(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}} + \\
&+ |(A_1 A_2)BC(D_1 D_2)\rangle(1 - \delta_{A_1 B \text{ no sum}}) + |(A_1 A_2)BC(D_1 D_2)\rangle(1 - \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}})) = \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (\text{blank} + \text{blank} + \\
&+ (-1)\epsilon^{BD_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{A_1 C} (1 - \delta_{A_1 B \text{ no sum}}) + (-1)\epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{BD_2} \epsilon^{A_2 C} (1 - \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&+ \text{blank} + \text{blank} + \\
&+ (-1)\epsilon^{BD_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{A_1 C} (1 - \delta_{A_1 B \text{ no sum}}) + (-1)\epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{BD_2} \epsilon^{A_2 C} (1 - \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&+ (-1)\epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{BC} \delta_{A_1 B \text{ no sum}} + (-1)\epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{BC} \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}} + \\
&+ \epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{BC} (1 - \delta_{A_1 B \text{ no sum}}) + \epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{BC} (1 - \delta_{A_2 B \text{ no sum}})) |(A_1 A_2)BC(D_1 D_2)\rangle = \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (2s - 4(s - r)) = r - \frac{1}{2}s
\end{aligned} \tag{111}$$

Note: Similar comments as in previous calculation. Moreover the relabelling $A_1 \equiv A_2$ and $D_1 \equiv D_2$ in the second and fourth line allows the epsilon product to be read as one of the elementary vectors.

4.3 Operators acting on the (v_0, v_1) basis

Considering equations (101), (102), (107), (108), (109), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12}v_0 &= -\frac{1}{2}v_0 \\
D_{12}v_1 &= v_1
\end{aligned} \tag{112}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{13}v_0 &= \frac{5}{6}v_0 - \frac{4}{9}v_1 \\
D_{13}v_1 &= -\frac{1}{2}v_0 - \frac{1}{3}v_1
\end{aligned} \tag{113}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{14}v_0 &= \frac{5}{3}v_0 + \frac{4}{9}v_1 \\
D_{14}v_1 &= \frac{1}{2}v_0 + \frac{4}{3}v_1
\end{aligned} \tag{114}$$

Note that the D_{12} operator is diagonal on the (v_0, v_1) basis.

As for the squared areas, considering equation (6), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11}v_0 &= -2v_0 \\
D_{11}v_1 &= -2v_1
\end{aligned} \tag{115}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{22}v_0 &= -\frac{3}{4}v_0 \\
D_{22}v_1 &= -\frac{3}{4}v_1
\end{aligned} \tag{116}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{33}v_0 &= -\frac{3}{4}v_0 \\
D_{33}v_1 &= -\frac{3}{4}v_1
\end{aligned} \tag{117}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{44}v_0 &= -2v_0 \\
D_{44}v_1 &= -2v_1
\end{aligned} \tag{118}$$

As per equation (9), the squared volume operator is defined as $V^2 = \frac{2}{9}[D_{13}, D_{12}]$. Considering equations (112), (113), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
V^2v_0 &= \frac{4}{27}v_1 \\
V^2v_1 &= -\frac{1}{6}v_0
\end{aligned} \tag{119}$$

4.4 Maximal commuting subalgebra $(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{33}, D_{44}, D_{12})$ on the (v_0, v_1) basis

On the (v_0, v_1) basis, the maximal commuting subalgebra shows as $(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{33}, D_{44}, D_{12})$. Here below the observables on the respective basis elements.

4.4.1 Observables on the v_0 basis element

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11,v_0} &= -2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{dimensional } D_{11,v_0} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
D_{22,v_0} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{dimensional } D_{22,v_0} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
D_{33,v_0} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{dimensional } D_{33,v_0} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
D_{44,v_0} &= -2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{dimensional } D_{44,v_0} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \textit{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{120}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12,v_0} &= -\frac{1}{2} \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{normalized } D_{12,v_0} &= -\frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{angle}_{12,v_0} &= 114.1^\circ \quad \textit{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{121}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{v_0} &= \frac{5}{6} \quad \textit{expectation value} \\
\textit{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{v_0} &= \frac{5}{3\sqrt{6}} \quad \textit{expectation value} \\
\langle \textit{angle}_{13} \rangle_{v_0} &= 47.1^\circ \quad \textit{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{13},v_0} &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} \\
\textit{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13},v_0} &= \frac{2}{3\sqrt{3}} \approx 0.385 \\
\frac{5}{3\sqrt{6}} - \frac{2}{3\sqrt{3}} &\leq \textit{normalized } D_{13,v_0} \leq \frac{5}{3\sqrt{6}} + \frac{2}{3\sqrt{3}} \quad \textit{fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \textit{angle}_{13,v_0} \leq 72.8^\circ \quad \textit{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{122}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{v_0} &= \frac{5}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{14} \rangle_{v_0} &= \frac{5}{6} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{14} \rangle_{v_0} &= 33.6^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{14}, v_0} &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{14}, v_0} &= \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}} \approx 0.236 \\
\frac{5}{6} - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{14, v_0} \leq \frac{5}{6} + \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{14, v_0} \leq 53.3^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{123}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle V^2 \rangle_{v_0} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{dimensional } \langle V^2 \rangle_{v_0} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{V^2, v_0} &= \frac{\sqrt{2}i}{9} \\
\text{dimensional } \sigma_{V^2, v_0} &= -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{9} a_0^3 \\
-\frac{\sqrt{2}i}{9} &\leq V_{v_0}^2 \leq \frac{\sqrt{2}i}{9} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{9} a_0^3 &\leq \text{dimensional } V_{v_0}^2 \leq \frac{\sqrt{2}}{9} a_0^3 \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{124}$$

As for the +ve/-ve dimensional squared volume, refer to the remark at the end of paragraph 3.4.1.

4.4.2 Observables on the v_1 basis element

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11, v_1} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{11, v_1} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{22, v_1} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{22, v_1} &= \frac{3}{4} a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{33, v_1} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{33, v_1} &= \frac{3}{4} a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{44, v_1} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{44, v_1} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{125}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12,v_1} &= 1 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{normalized } D_{12,v_1} &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{angle}_{12,v_1} &= 35.3^\circ \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{126}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{v_1} &= -\frac{1}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{v_1} &= -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{3\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{13} \rangle_{v_1} &= 105.8^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{13,v_1}} &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13,v_1}} &= \frac{2}{3\sqrt{3}} \approx 0.385 \\
-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{3\sqrt{3}} - \frac{2}{3\sqrt{3}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{13,v_1} \leq -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{3\sqrt{3}} + \frac{2}{3\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
83.5^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{13,v_1} \leq 131.1^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{127}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{v_1} &= \frac{4}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{14} \rangle_{v_1} &= \frac{2}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{14} \rangle_{v_1} &= 48.2^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{14,v_1}} &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{14,v_1}} &= \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}} \approx 0.236 \\
\frac{2}{3} - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{14,v_1} \leq \frac{2}{3} + \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
25.5^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{14,v_1} \leq 64.5^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{128}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle V^2 \rangle_{v_1} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{dimensional } \langle V^2 \rangle_{v_1} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{V^2, v_1} &= \frac{\sqrt{2}i}{9} \\
\text{dimensional } \sigma_{V^2, v_1} &= -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{9}a_0^3 \quad (129) \\
-\frac{\sqrt{2}i}{9} &\leq V_{v_1}^2 \leq \frac{\sqrt{2}i}{9} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{9}a_0^3 &\leq \text{dimensional } V_{v_1}^2 \leq \frac{\sqrt{2}}{9}a_0^3 \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned}$$

As for the +ve/-ve dimensional squared volume, refer to the remark at the end of paragraph 3.4.1.

4.5 Maximal commuting subalgebra $(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{33}, D_{44}, V^2)$ on the (f_1, f_2) basis

Let's diagonalize the squared volume operator V^2 . Working on the (v_0, v_1) basis and looking for the eigenvalues μ and eigenstates f , solutions to $V^2 f = \mu f$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu_1 &= \frac{\sqrt{2}i}{9} \\
\mu_2 &= -\frac{\sqrt{2}i}{9} \\
f_1 &= v_0 - \frac{2\sqrt{2}i}{3}v_1 \\
f_2 &= v_0 + \frac{2\sqrt{2}i}{3}v_1
\end{aligned} \quad (130)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
v_0 &= \frac{1}{2}(f_1 + f_2) \\
v_1 &= \frac{3i}{4\sqrt{2}}(f_1 - f_2)
\end{aligned} \quad (131)$$

also

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1^\dagger f_1 &= 8 \\
f_2^\dagger f_2 &= 8 \\
f_1^\dagger f_2 &= 0
\end{aligned} \quad (132)$$

hence, the (f_1, f_2) basis is orthogonal.

On the (f_1, f_2) basis, the maximal commuting subalgebra shows as $(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{33}, D_{44}, V^2)$.

4.5.1 Operators acting on the (f_1, f_2) basis

$$\begin{aligned} D_{12}f_1 &= \frac{1}{4}f_1 - \frac{3}{4}f_2 \\ D_{12}f_2 &= -\frac{3}{4}f_1 + \frac{1}{4}f_2 \end{aligned} \tag{133}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{13}f_1 &= \frac{1}{4}f_1 + \left(\frac{7}{12} + \frac{\sqrt{2}i}{3}\right)f_2 \\ D_{13}f_2 &= \left(\frac{7}{12} - \frac{\sqrt{2}i}{3}\right)f_1 + \frac{1}{4}f_2 \end{aligned} \tag{134}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{14}f_1 &= \frac{3}{2}f_1 + \left(\frac{1}{6} - \frac{\sqrt{2}i}{3}\right)f_2 \\ D_{14}f_2 &= \left(\frac{1}{6} + \frac{\sqrt{2}i}{3}\right)f_1 + \frac{3}{2}f_2 \end{aligned} \tag{135}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{11}f_1 &= -2f_1 \\ D_{11}f_2 &= -2f_2 \end{aligned} \tag{136}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{22}f_1 &= -\frac{3}{4}f_1 \\ D_{22}f_2 &= -\frac{3}{4}f_2 \end{aligned} \tag{137}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{33}f_1 &= -\frac{3}{4}f_1 \\ D_{33}f_2 &= -\frac{3}{4}f_2 \end{aligned} \tag{138}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{44}f_1 &= -2f_1 \\ D_{44}f_2 &= -2f_2 \end{aligned} \tag{139}$$

$$\begin{aligned} V^2f_1 &= \frac{\sqrt{2}i}{9}f_1 \\ V^2f_2 &= -\frac{\sqrt{2}i}{9}f_2 \end{aligned} \tag{140}$$

Here below the observables on the respective basis elements.

4.5.2 Observables on the f_1 basis element

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11,f_1} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{11,f_1} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{22,f_1} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{22,f_1} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{33,f_1} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{33,f_1} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{44,f_1} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{44,f_1} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{141}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{12} \rangle_{f_1} &= \frac{1}{4} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{12} \rangle_{f_1} &= \frac{1}{2\sqrt{6}} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{12} \rangle_{f_1} &= 78.2^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{12},f_1} &= \frac{3}{4} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{12},f_1} &= \frac{3}{2\sqrt{6}} \approx 0.612 \\
\frac{1}{2\sqrt{6}} - \frac{3}{2\sqrt{6}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{12,f_1} \leq \frac{1}{2\sqrt{6}} + \frac{3}{2\sqrt{6}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
35.3^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{12,f_1} \leq 114.1^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{142}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{f_1} &= \frac{1}{4} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{f_1} &= \frac{1}{2\sqrt{6}} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{13} \rangle_{f_1} &= 78.2^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{13},f_1} &= \frac{3}{4} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13},f_1} &= \frac{3}{2\sqrt{6}} \approx 0.612 \\
\frac{1}{2\sqrt{6}} - \frac{3}{2\sqrt{6}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{13,f_1} \leq \frac{1}{2\sqrt{6}} + \frac{3}{2\sqrt{6}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
35.3^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{13,f_1} \leq 114.1^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{143}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{f_1} &= \frac{3}{2} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{14} \rangle_{f_1} &= \frac{3}{4} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{14} \rangle_{f_1} &= 41.4^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{14}, f_1} &= \frac{1}{2} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{14}, f_1} &= \frac{1}{4} = 0.250 \\
\frac{3}{4} - \frac{1}{4} \leq \text{normalized } D_{14}, f_1 &\leq \frac{3}{4} + \frac{1}{4} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
0^\circ \leq \text{angle}_{14}, f_1 &\leq 60^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{144}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{f_1}^2 &= \frac{\sqrt{2}i}{9} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } V_{f_1}^2 &= -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{9}a_0^3 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{145}$$

4.5.3 Observables on the f_2 basis element

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11, f_2} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{11, f_2} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{22, f_2} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{22, f_2} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{33, f_2} &= -\frac{3}{4} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{33, f_2} &= \frac{3}{4}a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{44, f_2} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{44, f_2} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{146}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{12} \rangle_{f_2} &= \frac{1}{4} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{12} \rangle_{f_2} &= \frac{1}{2\sqrt{6}} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{12} \rangle_{f_2} &= 78.2^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{12}, f_2} &= \frac{3}{4} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{12}, f_2} &= \frac{3}{2\sqrt{6}} \approx 0.612 \\
\frac{1}{2\sqrt{6}} - \frac{3}{2\sqrt{6}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{12, f_2} \leq \frac{1}{2\sqrt{6}} + \frac{3}{2\sqrt{6}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
35.3^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{12, f_2} \leq 114.1^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{147}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{f_2} &= \frac{1}{4} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{f_2} &= \frac{1}{2\sqrt{6}} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{13} \rangle_{f_2} &= 78.2^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{13}, f_2} &= \frac{3}{4} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13}, f_2} &= \frac{3}{2\sqrt{6}} \approx 0.612 \\
\frac{1}{2\sqrt{6}} - \frac{3}{2\sqrt{6}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{13, f_2} \leq \frac{1}{2\sqrt{6}} + \frac{3}{2\sqrt{6}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
35.3^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{13, f_2} \leq 114.1^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{148}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{f_2} &= \frac{3}{2} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{14} \rangle_{f_2} &= \frac{3}{4} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{14} \rangle_{f_2} &= 41.4^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{14}, f_2} &= \frac{1}{2} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{14}, f_2} &= \frac{1}{4} = 0.250 \\
\frac{3}{4} - \frac{1}{4} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{14, f_2} \leq \frac{3}{4} + \frac{1}{4} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{14, f_2} \leq 60^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{149}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{f_2}^2 &= -\frac{\sqrt{2}i}{9} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } V_{f_2}^2 &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{9} a_0^3 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{150}$$

As for the +ve/-ve dimensional squared volume, on the f_2/f_1 basis elements respectively, refer to the remark at the end of paragraph 3.4.1.

4.6 A general spin network in the representation $(1, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 1)$

Any spin network can be written as a linear combination of the elements of a basis. As the isotropic subspace of the representation $(1, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 1)$ is 2-dimensional, as well as the representation $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$, considerations similar to what in paragraph 3.6 show up, so that the general spin network is a qubit as well.

5 Representation $(1, 1, 1, 1)$

Let's move to a further higher spin representation, e.g. $j_1 = 1, j_2 = 1, j_3 = 1, j_4 = 1$, corresponding to the tensor product $\rho^{(1)} \otimes \rho^{(1)} \otimes \rho^{(1)} \otimes \rho^{(1)}$. Description in figure 9.

Figure 9: Representation $(1, 1, 1, 1)$

Expanding the tensor product to irreducible representations, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
1 \otimes 1 \otimes 1 \otimes 1 &= (2 \oplus 1 \oplus 0) \otimes (2 \oplus 1 \oplus 0) = \\
&= (4 \oplus 3 \oplus 2 \oplus 1 \oplus 0) \oplus (3 \oplus 2 \oplus 1) \oplus 2 \oplus (3 \oplus 2 \oplus 1) \oplus \\
&\oplus (2 \oplus 1 \oplus 0) \oplus 1 \oplus 2 \oplus 1 \oplus 0 = \\
&= 4 \oplus 3^3 \oplus 2^6 \oplus 1^6 \oplus 0^3
\end{aligned} \tag{151}$$

and so, the isotropic subspace is 3-dimensional.

5.1 A basis of the isotropic subspace

To determine a basis, let's apply what in paragraph 2.6.2 at this representation

$$2 - k_{12} = j = 2 - k_{34} \quad 0 \leq k_{12} \leq 2 \quad 0 \leq k_{34} \leq 2 \quad (152)$$

hence

$$\begin{array}{ccc} k_{12} & j & k_{34} \\ 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 2 & 0 & 2 \end{array} \quad (153)$$

That means

$$\begin{aligned} w_{12,j=2} &= \epsilon^{A_1 E_1} \epsilon^{A_2 E_2} \epsilon^{B_1 E_3} \epsilon^{B_2 E_4} e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_{B_1 B_2} \otimes e_{E_1 E_2 E_3 E_4} \\ w_{34,j=2} &= \delta_{F_1}^{C_1} \delta_{F_2}^{C_2} \delta_{F_3}^{D_1} \delta_{F_4}^{D_2} e_{C_1 C_2} \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \otimes e^{F_1 F_2 F_3 F_4} \\ u_0 &= w_{12,j=2} \otimes w_{34,j=2} \end{aligned} \quad (154)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} w_{12,j=1} &= \epsilon^{A_1 B_1} \epsilon^{A_2 E_1} \epsilon^{B_2 E_2} e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_{B_1 B_2} \otimes e_{E_1 E_2} \\ w_{34,j=1} &= \delta_{F_1}^{C_1} \epsilon^{C_2 D_2} \delta_{F_2}^{D_1} e_{C_1 C_2} \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \otimes e^{F_1 F_2} \\ u_1 &= w_{12,j=1} \otimes w_{34,j=1} \end{aligned} \quad (155)$$

also

$$\begin{aligned} w_{12,j=0} &= \epsilon^{A_1 B_1} \epsilon^{A_2 B_2} e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_{B_1 B_2} \\ w_{34,j=0} &= \epsilon^{C_1 D_1} \epsilon^{C_2 D_2} e_{C_1 C_2} \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \\ u_2 &= w_{12,j=0} \otimes w_{34,j=0} \end{aligned} \quad (156)$$

where $e_{AB} = e_A \odot e_B$ and $e_{ABCD} = e_A \odot e_B \odot e_C \odot e_D$, symmetrized tensor product. Note also that the virtual link j is assumed incoming to the algebraic $w_{12,j}$ and consequently outgoing from the algebraic $w_{34,j}$, thus explaining the dual basis.

So, a basis of the 3-dimensional isotropic subspace is

$$\begin{aligned} u_0 &= \epsilon^{(A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2}) e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_{B_1 B_2} \otimes e_{C_1 C_2} \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \\ u_1 &= \epsilon^{A_1 B_1} \epsilon^{(A_2 C_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_1)} \epsilon^{C_2 D_2} e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_{B_1 B_2} \otimes e_{C_1 C_2} \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \\ u_2 &= \epsilon^{A_1 B_1} \epsilon^{A_2 B_2} \epsilon^{C_1 D_1} \epsilon^{C_2 D_2} e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_{B_1 B_2} \otimes e_{C_1 C_2} \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \end{aligned} \quad (157)$$

where $e^{ABCD} \otimes e_{EFGH} = \delta_E^{(A} \delta_F^B \delta_G^C \delta_H^D)$.

However, for computational convenience, let's express the (u_0, u_1, u_2) basis against the following elementary vectors

$$\begin{aligned} l &= \epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_{B_1 B_2} \otimes e_{C_1 C_2} \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \\ m &= \epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{B_1 C_1} \epsilon^{B_2 C_2} e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_{B_1 B_2} \otimes e_{C_1 C_2} \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \\ n &= \epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{B_1 C_2} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_{B_1 B_2} \otimes e_{C_1 C_2} \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} \end{aligned} \quad (158)$$

Here below the graphical description.

Figure 10: l elementary vector

Figure 11: m elementary vector

Figure 12: n elementary vector

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_0 &= \frac{1}{6}l + \frac{1}{6}m + \frac{2}{3}n \\
 u_1 &= \frac{1}{2}l - \frac{1}{2}m \\
 u_2 &= l + m - 2n
 \end{aligned} \tag{159}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 l &= u_0 + u_1 + \frac{1}{3}u_2 \\
 m &= u_0 - u_1 + \frac{1}{3}u_2 \\
 n &= u_0 - \frac{1}{6}u_2
 \end{aligned} \tag{160}$$

Note: As there are more elementary vectors than the dimension of the isotropic subspace, to get the relation between the elementary vectors or between the (u_0, u_1, u_2) basis and the elementary vectors, just write the latter as linear combinations of the former and then use the identities in equation (33).

For later use, let's compose the elementary vectors

$$\begin{aligned}
 l^\dagger l &= 9 \\
 m^\dagger m &= 9 \\
 n^\dagger n &= \frac{21}{4} \\
 l^\dagger m &= 3 \\
 l^\dagger n &= \frac{9}{2} \\
 m^\dagger n &= \frac{9}{2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{161}$$

Here below a few examples, how they are calculated:

$$\begin{aligned}
l^\dagger l &= \epsilon_{A_1 C_1} \epsilon_{A_2 C_2} \epsilon_{B_1 D_1} \epsilon_{B_2 D_2} \epsilon^{E_1 G_1} \epsilon^{E_2 G_2} \epsilon^{F_1 H_1} \epsilon^{F_2 H_2} \times \\
&\times e^{A_1 A_2} \otimes e^{B_1 B_2} \otimes e^{C_1 C_2} \otimes e^{D_1 D_2} e_{E_1 E_2} \otimes e_{F_1 F_2} \otimes e_{G_1 G_2} \otimes e_{H_1 H_2} = \\
&= \epsilon_{(A_1 C_1} \epsilon_{A_2 C_2)} \epsilon_{B_1 D_1} \epsilon_{B_2 D_2} \epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{(B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2)} = \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (\epsilon_{A_1 C_1} \epsilon_{A_2 C_2} \epsilon_{B_1 D_1} \epsilon_{B_2 D_2} + \epsilon_{A_1 C_2} \epsilon_{A_2 C_1} \epsilon_{B_1 D_1} \epsilon_{B_2 D_2}) \times \\
&\times (\epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} + \epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_2} \epsilon^{B_2 D_1}) = \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 + 2 \times 2 \times 2 + 2 \times 2 \times 2 + 2 \times 2) = 9
\end{aligned} \tag{162}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
l^\dagger m &= \epsilon_{A_1 C_1} \epsilon_{A_2 C_2} \epsilon_{B_1 D_1} \epsilon_{B_2 D_2} \epsilon^{E_1 H_1} \epsilon^{E_2 H_2} \epsilon^{F_1 G_1} \epsilon^{F_2 G_2} \times \\
&\times e^{A_1 A_2} \otimes e^{B_1 B_2} \otimes e^{C_1 C_2} \otimes e^{D_1 D_2} e_{E_1 E_2} \otimes e_{F_1 F_2} \otimes e_{G_1 G_2} \otimes e_{H_1 H_2} = \\
&= \epsilon_{A_1 C_1} \epsilon_{A_2 C_2} \epsilon_{B_1 D_1} \epsilon_{B_2 D_2} \epsilon^{(A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2)} \epsilon^{(B_1 C_1} \epsilon^{B_2 C_2)} = \\
&= \epsilon_{A_1 C_1} \epsilon_{A_2 C_2} \epsilon_{B_1 D_1} \epsilon_{B_2 D_2} \frac{1}{4} (\epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{B_1 C_1} \epsilon^{B_2 C_2} + \\
&+ \epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} \epsilon^{B_1 C_2} \epsilon^{B_2 C_1} + \epsilon^{A_1 D_2} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{B_1 C_1} \epsilon^{B_2 C_2} + \\
&+ \epsilon^{A_1 D_2} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{B_1 C_2} \epsilon^{B_2 C_1}) = \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (2 \times 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 \times 2) = 3
\end{aligned} \tag{163}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
l^\dagger n &= \epsilon_{A_1 C_1} \epsilon_{A_2 C_2} \epsilon_{B_1 D_1} \epsilon_{B_2 D_2} \epsilon^{E_1 G_1} \epsilon^{E_2 H_1} \epsilon^{F_1 G_2} \epsilon^{F_2 H_2} \times \\
&\times e^{A_1 A_2} \otimes e^{B_1 B_2} \otimes e^{C_1 C_2} \otimes e^{D_1 D_2} e_{E_1 E_2} \otimes e_{F_1 F_2} \otimes e_{G_1 G_2} \otimes e_{H_1 H_2} = \\
&= \epsilon_{(A_1 C_1} \epsilon_{A_2 C_2)} \epsilon_{(B_1 D_1} \epsilon_{B_2 D_2)} \epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{B_1 C_2} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} = \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (\epsilon_{A_1 C_1} \epsilon_{A_2 C_2} \epsilon_{B_1 D_1} \epsilon_{B_2 D_2} + \epsilon_{A_1 C_1} \epsilon_{A_2 C_2} \epsilon_{B_1 D_2} \epsilon_{B_2 D_1} + \\
&+ \epsilon_{A_1 C_2} \epsilon_{A_2 C_1} \epsilon_{B_1 D_1} \epsilon_{B_2 D_2} + \epsilon_{A_1 C_2} \epsilon_{A_2 C_1} \epsilon_{B_1 D_2} \epsilon_{B_2 D_1}) \times \\
&\times \epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{B_1 C_2} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} = \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (2 \times 2 \times 2 + 2 \times 2 + 2 \times 2 + 2) = \frac{9}{2}
\end{aligned} \tag{164}$$

Using equations (159) and (161), we can compose the (u_o, u_1, u_2) basis

$$\begin{aligned}
u_0^\dagger u_0 &= 5 \\
u_1^\dagger u_1 &= 3 \\
u_2^\dagger u_2 &= 9 \\
u_0^\dagger u_1 &= 0 \\
u_0^\dagger u_2 &= 0 \\
u_1^\dagger u_2 &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{165}$$

hence, the (u_o, u_1, u_2) basis is orthogonal.

5.2 Operators acting on the elementary vectors

The invariant operators act on the elementary vectors as

$$\begin{aligned}D_{12}l &= l - 2n \\D_{12}m &= m - 2n \\D_{12}n &= -\frac{1}{2}l - \frac{1}{2}m\end{aligned}\tag{166}$$

$$\begin{aligned}D_{13}l &= 2l \\D_{13}m &= -m + 2n \\D_{13}n &= \frac{1}{2}l + n\end{aligned}\tag{167}$$

$$\begin{aligned}D_{14}l &= -l + 2n \\D_{14}m &= 2m \\D_{14}n &= \frac{1}{2}m + n\end{aligned}\tag{168}$$

Here below, as an example, how the action of the operator D_{12} is calculated. To

simplify the notation, let's define $e_{A_1 A_2} \otimes e_{B_1 B_2} \otimes e_{C_1 C_2} \otimes e_{D_1 D_2} = |(A_1 A_2)(B_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle$.

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12}l &= \vec{L}_1 \cdot \vec{L}_2 \epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} |(A_1 A_2)(B_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle = \\
&= \epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} \times \\
&\quad \times (|((\tau_x A_1) A_2)((\tau_x B_1) B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle + |((\tau_x A_1) A_2)(B_1(\tau_x B_2))(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle + \\
&\quad + |(A_1(\tau_x A_2))((\tau_x B_1) B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle + |(A_1(\tau_x A_2))(B_1(\tau_x B_2))(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle + \\
&\quad + |((\tau_y A_1) A_2)((\tau_y B_1) B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle + |((\tau_y A_1) A_2)(B_1(\tau_y B_2))(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle + \\
&\quad + |(A_1(\tau_y A_2))((\tau_y B_1) B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle + |(A_1(\tau_y A_2))(B_1(\tau_y B_2))(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle + \\
&\quad + |((\tau_z A_1) A_2)((\tau_z B_1) B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle + |((\tau_z A_1) A_2)(B_1(\tau_z B_2))(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle + \\
&\quad + |(A_1(\tau_z A_2))((\tau_z B_1) B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle + |(A_1(\tau_z A_2))(B_1(\tau_z B_2))(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle) = \\
&= \epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} \times \\
&\quad \times \frac{1}{4} ((-1)|(C_1 A_2)(D_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_1 B_1 \text{ no sum}} + (-1)|(C_1 A_2)(B_1 D_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_1 B_2 \text{ no sum}} + \\
&\quad + (-1)|(A_1 C_2)(D_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_2 B_1 \text{ no sum}} + (-1)|(A_1 C_2)(B_1 D_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_2 B_2 \text{ no sum}} + \\
&\quad + (-1)|(B_1 A_2)(A_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_1 B_1 \text{ no sum}}) + (-1)|(B_2 A_2)(B_1 A_1)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_1 B_2 \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&\quad + (-1)|(A_1 B_1)(A_2 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_2 B_1 \text{ no sum}}) + (-1)|(A_1 B_2)(B_1 A_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_2 B_2 \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&\quad + |(C_1 A_2)(D_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_1 B_1 \text{ no sum}} + |(C_1 A_2)(B_1 D_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_1 B_2 \text{ no sum}} + \\
&\quad + |(A_1 C_2)(D_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_2 B_1 \text{ no sum}} + |(A_1 C_2)(B_1 D_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_2 B_2 \text{ no sum}} + \\
&\quad + (-1)|(B_1 A_2)(A_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_1 B_1 \text{ no sum}}) + (-1)|(B_2 A_2)(B_1 A_1)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_1 B_2 \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&\quad + (-1)|(A_1 B_1)(A_2 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_2 B_1 \text{ no sum}}) + (-1)|(A_1 B_2)(B_1 A_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_2 B_2 \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&\quad + (-1)|(A_1 A_2)(B_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_1 B_1 \text{ no sum}} + (-1)|(A_1 A_2)(B_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_1 B_2 \text{ no sum}} + \\
&\quad + (-1)|(A_1 A_2)(B_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_2 B_1 \text{ no sum}} + (-1)|(A_1 A_2)(B_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle \delta_{A_2 B_2 \text{ no sum}} + \\
&\quad + |(A_1 A_2)(B_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_1 B_1 \text{ no sum}}) + |(A_1 A_2)(B_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_1 B_2 \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&\quad + |(A_1 A_2)(B_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_2 B_1 \text{ no sum}}) + |(A_1 A_2)(B_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle (1 - \delta_{A_2 B_2 \text{ no sum}})) = \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (\text{blank} + \text{blank} + \\
&\quad + \text{blank} + \text{blank} + \\
&\quad + (-1)\epsilon^{B_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} (1 - \delta_{A_1 B_1 \text{ no sum}}) + (-1)\epsilon^{B_2 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_1 D_2} (1 - \delta_{A_1 B_2 \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&\quad + (-1)\epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{B_1 C_2} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} (1 - \delta_{A_2 B_1 \text{ no sum}}) + (-1)\epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{B_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} (1 - \delta_{A_2 B_2 \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&\quad + \text{blank} + \text{blank} + \\
&\quad + \text{blank} + \text{blank} + \\
&\quad + (-1)\epsilon^{B_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{A_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} (1 - \delta_{A_1 B_1 \text{ no sum}}) + (-1)\epsilon^{B_2 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_1 D_2} (1 - \delta_{A_1 B_2 \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&\quad + (-1)\epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{B_1 C_2} \epsilon^{A_2 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} (1 - \delta_{A_2 B_1 \text{ no sum}}) + (-1)\epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{B_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{A_2 D_2} (1 - \delta_{A_2 B_2 \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&\quad + (-1)\epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} \delta_{A_1 B_1 \text{ no sum}} + (-1)\epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} \delta_{A_1 B_2 \text{ no sum}} + \\
&\quad + (-1)\epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} \delta_{A_2 B_1 \text{ no sum}} + (-1)\epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} \delta_{A_2 B_2 \text{ no sum}} + \\
&\quad + \epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} (1 - \delta_{A_1 B_1 \text{ no sum}}) + \epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} (1 - \delta_{A_1 B_2 \text{ no sum}}) + \\
&\quad + \epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} (1 - \delta_{A_2 B_1 \text{ no sum}}) + \epsilon^{A_1 C_1} \epsilon^{A_2 C_2} \epsilon^{B_1 D_1} \epsilon^{B_2 D_2} (1 - \delta_{A_2 B_2 \text{ no sum}})) \times \\
&\quad \times |(A_1 A_2)(B_1 B_2)(C_1 C_2)(D_1 D_2)\rangle = \\
&= \frac{1}{4} (l - 2n + l - 2n + l - 2n + l - 2n) = l - 2n
\end{aligned}$$

(169)

Note: The action of the τ 's splits each line in two lines whether the acted indices are equal, $\Rightarrow \delta_{A_1 B_1 \text{ no sum}}$, $\Rightarrow \delta_{A_1 B_2 \text{ no sum}}$ and so on, or not equal, $\Rightarrow (1 - \delta_{A_1 B_1 \text{ no sum}})$, $\Rightarrow (1 - \delta_{A_1 B_2 \text{ no sum}})$ and so on. The action of the τ 's, refer to equation (5), is consequent. What in the first/second and fifth/sixth lines cancel each other (a *blank* is posted for an easy reading). The relabeling $A_1 \rightleftharpoons B_1$, $A_1 \rightleftharpoons B_2$ and so on, in the third/forth and seventh/eighth lines, allows the epsilon product to be read as one of the elementary vectors. The terms with the constraint on the indices cancel one another.

5.3 Operators acting on the (u_0, u_1, u_2) basis

Considering equations (159), (160), (166), (167), (168), we have

$$\begin{aligned} D_{12}u_0 &= -u_0 \\ D_{12}u_1 &= u_1 \\ D_{12}u_2 &= 2u_2 \end{aligned} \tag{170}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{13}u_0 &= \frac{3}{2}u_0 + \frac{5}{6}u_1 \\ D_{13}u_1 &= \frac{1}{2}u_0 + \frac{1}{2}u_1 + \frac{2}{3}u_2 \\ D_{13}u_2 &= 2u_1 \end{aligned} \tag{171}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{14}u_0 &= \frac{3}{2}u_0 - \frac{5}{6}u_1 \\ D_{14}u_1 &= -\frac{1}{2}u_0 + \frac{1}{2}u_1 - \frac{2}{3}u_2 \\ D_{14}u_2 &= -2u_1 \end{aligned} \tag{172}$$

Note that the D_{12} operator is diagonal on the (u_0, u_1, u_2) basis.

As for the squared areas, considering equation (6), we have

$$\begin{aligned} D_{11}u_0 &= -2u_0 \\ D_{11}u_1 &= -2u_1 \\ D_{11}u_2 &= -2u_2 \end{aligned} \tag{173}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{22}u_0 &= -2u_0 \\ D_{22}u_1 &= -2u_1 \\ D_{22}u_2 &= -2u_2 \end{aligned} \tag{174}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{33}u_0 &= -2u_0 \\ D_{33}u_1 &= -2u_1 \\ D_{33}u_2 &= -2u_2 \end{aligned} \tag{175}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{44}u_0 &= -2u_0 \\
D_{44}u_1 &= -2u_1 \\
D_{44}u_2 &= -2u_2
\end{aligned} \tag{176}$$

As per equation (9), the squared volume operator is defined as $V^2 = \frac{2}{9}[D_{13}, D_{12}]$. Considering equations (170), (171), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
V^2u_0 &= -\frac{10}{27}u_1 \\
V^2u_1 &= \frac{2}{9}u_0 - \frac{4}{27}u_2 \\
V^2u_2 &= \frac{4}{9}u_1
\end{aligned} \tag{177}$$

5.4 Maximal commuting subalgebra $(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{33}, D_{44}, D_{12})$ on the (u_0, u_1, u_2) basis

On the (u_0, u_1, u_2) basis, the maximal commuting subalgebra shows as $(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{33}, D_{44}, D_{12})$. Here below the observables on the respective basis elements.

5.4.1 Observables on the u_0 basis element

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11,u_0} &= -2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{dimensional } D_{11,u_0} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
D_{22,u_0} &= -2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{dimensional } D_{22,u_0} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
D_{33,u_0} &= -2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{dimensional } D_{33,u_0} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
D_{44,u_0} &= -2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{dimensional } D_{44,u_0} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \textit{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{178}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12,u_0} &= -1 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{normalized } D_{12,u_0} &= -\frac{1}{2} \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{angle}_{12,u_0} &= 120^\circ \quad \textit{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{179}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{u_0} &= \frac{3}{2} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{u_0} &= \frac{3}{4} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{13} \rangle_{u_0} &= 41.4^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{13}, u_0} &= \frac{\sqrt{5}}{2\sqrt{3}} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13}, u_0} &= \frac{\sqrt{5}}{4\sqrt{3}} \approx 0.323 \\
\frac{3}{4} - \frac{\sqrt{5}}{4\sqrt{3}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{13, u_0} \leq \frac{3}{4} + \frac{\sqrt{5}}{4\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{13, u_0} \leq 64.7^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{180}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{u_0} &= \frac{3}{2} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{14} \rangle_{u_0} &= \frac{3}{4} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{14} \rangle_{u_0} &= 41.4^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{14}, u_0} &= \frac{\sqrt{5}}{2\sqrt{3}} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{14}, u_0} &= \frac{\sqrt{5}}{4\sqrt{3}} \approx 0.323 \\
\frac{3}{4} - \frac{\sqrt{5}}{4\sqrt{3}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{14, u_0} \leq \frac{3}{4} + \frac{\sqrt{5}}{4\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{14, u_0} \leq 64.7^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{181}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle V^2 \rangle_{u_0} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{dimensional } \langle V^2 \rangle_{u_0} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{V^2, u_0} &= \frac{2\sqrt{5}i}{9\sqrt{3}} \\
\text{dimensional } \sigma_{V^2, u_0} &= -\frac{2\sqrt{5}}{9\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 \\
-\frac{2\sqrt{5}i}{9\sqrt{3}} &\leq V_{u_0}^2 \leq \frac{2\sqrt{5}i}{9\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
-\frac{2\sqrt{5}}{9\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 &\leq \text{dimensional } V_{u_0}^2 \leq \frac{2\sqrt{5}}{9\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{182}$$

As for the +ve/-ve dimensional squared volume, refer to the remark at the end of paragraph 3.4.1.

5.4.2 Observables on the u_1 basis element

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11,u_1} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{11,u_1} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{22,u_1} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{22,u_1} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{33,u_1} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{33,u_1} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{44,u_1} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{44,u_1} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{183}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12,u_1} &= 1 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{normalized } D_{12,u_1} &= \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{angle}_{12,u_1} &= 60^\circ \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{184}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{u_1} &= \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{u_1} &= \frac{1}{4} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{13} \rangle_{u_1} &= 75.5^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{13},u_1} &= \frac{\sqrt{7}}{2} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13},u_1} &= \frac{\sqrt{7}}{4} \approx 0.661 \\
\frac{1}{4} - \frac{\sqrt{7}}{4} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{13,u_1} \leq \frac{1}{4} + \frac{\sqrt{7}}{4} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
24.3^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{13,u_1} \leq 114.3^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{185}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{u_1} &= \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{14} \rangle_{u_1} &= \frac{1}{4} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{14} \rangle_{u_1} &= 75.5^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{14},u_1} &= \frac{\sqrt{7}}{2} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{14},u_1} &= \frac{\sqrt{7}}{4} \approx 0.661 \\
\frac{1}{4} - \frac{\sqrt{7}}{4} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{14,u_1} \leq \frac{1}{4} + \frac{\sqrt{7}}{4} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
24.3^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{14,u_1} \leq 114.3^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{186}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle V^2 \rangle_{u_1} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{dimensional } \langle V^2 \rangle_{u_1} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{V^2, u_1} &= \frac{2i}{3\sqrt{3}} \\
\text{dimensional } \sigma_{V^2, u_1} &= -\frac{2}{3\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 \quad (187) \\
-\frac{2i}{3\sqrt{3}} &\leq V_{u_1}^2 \leq \frac{2i}{3\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
-\frac{2}{3\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 &\leq \text{dimensional } V_{u_1}^2 \leq \frac{2}{3\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned}$$

As for the +ve/-ve dimensional squared volume, refer to the remark at the end of paragraph 3.4.1.

5.4.3 Observables on the u_2 basis element

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11, u_2} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{11, u_2} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{22, u_2} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{22, u_2} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{33, u_2} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{33, u_2} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{44, u_2} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{44, u_2} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \quad (188)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12, u_2} &= 2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{normalized } D_{12, u_2} &= 1 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{angle}_{12, u_2} &= 0^\circ \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \quad (189)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{u_2} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{u_2} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{13} \rangle_{u_2} &= 90^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{13}, u_2} &= \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13}, u_2} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \approx 0.577 \\
-\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{13, u_2} \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
54.7^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{13, u_2} \leq 125.3^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \quad (190)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{u_2} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{14} \rangle_{u_2} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{14} \rangle_{u_2} &= 90^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{14}, u_2} &= \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{14}, u_2} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \approx 0.577 \\
-\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{14, u_2} \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
54.7^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{14, u_2} \leq 125.3^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{191}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle V^2 \rangle_{u_2} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{dimensional } \langle V^2 \rangle_{u_2} &= 0 \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{V^2, u_2} &= \frac{4i}{9\sqrt{3}} \\
\text{dimensional } \sigma_{V^2, u_2} &= -\frac{4}{9\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 \\
-\frac{4i}{9\sqrt{3}} &\leq V_{u_2}^2 \leq \frac{4i}{9\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
-\frac{4}{9\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 &\leq \text{dimensional } V_{u_2}^2 \leq \frac{4}{9\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{192}$$

As for the +ve/-ve dimensional squared volume, refer to the remark at the end of paragraph 3.4.1.

5.5 Maximal commuting subalgebra $(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{33}, D_{44}, V^2)$ on the (g_1, g_2, g_3) basis

Let's diagonalize the squared volume operator V^2 . Working on the (u_0, u_1, u_2) basis and looking for the eigenvalues ν and eigenstates g , solutions to $V^2 g = \nu g$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\nu_1 &= 0 \\
\nu_2 &= \frac{2i}{3\sqrt{3}} \\
\nu_3 &= -\frac{2i}{3\sqrt{3}} \\
g_1 &= u_0 + \frac{5}{6}u_2 \\
g_2 &= u_0 + \sqrt{3}iu_1 - \frac{2}{3}u_2 \\
g_3 &= u_0 - \sqrt{3}iu_1 - \frac{2}{3}u_2
\end{aligned} \tag{193}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
u_0 &= \frac{4}{9}g_1 + \frac{5}{18}g_2 + \frac{5}{18}g_3 \\
u_1 &= -\frac{i}{2\sqrt{3}}g_2 + \frac{i}{2\sqrt{3}}g_3 \\
u_2 &= \frac{2}{3}g_1 - \frac{1}{3}g_2 - \frac{1}{3}g_3
\end{aligned} \tag{194}$$

also

$$\begin{aligned}
g_1^\dagger g_1 &= \frac{45}{4} \\
g_2^\dagger g_2 &= 18 \\
g_3^\dagger g_3 &= 18 \\
g_1^\dagger g_2 &= 0 \\
g_1^\dagger g_3 &= 0 \\
g_2^\dagger g_3 &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{195}$$

hence, the (g_1, g_2, g_3) basis is orthogonal.

On the (g_1, g_2, g_3) basis, the maximal commuting subalgebra shows as $(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{33}, D_{44}, V^2)$.

5.5.1 Operators acting on the (g_1, g_2, g_3) basis

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{12}g_1 &= \frac{2}{3}g_1 - \frac{5}{6}g_2 - \frac{5}{6}g_3 \\
D_{12}g_2 &= -\frac{4}{3}g_1 + \frac{2}{3}g_2 - \frac{1}{3}g_3 \\
D_{12}g_3 &= -\frac{4}{3}g_1 - \frac{1}{3}g_2 + \frac{2}{3}g_3
\end{aligned} \tag{196}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{13}g_1 &= \frac{2}{3}g_1 + \frac{5(1-\sqrt{3}i)}{12}g_2 + \frac{5(1+\sqrt{3}i)}{12}g_3 \\
D_{13}g_2 &= \frac{2(1+\sqrt{3}i)}{3}g_1 + \frac{2}{3}g_2 + \frac{(1-\sqrt{3}i)}{6}g_3 \\
D_{13}g_3 &= \frac{2(1-\sqrt{3}i)}{3}g_1 + \frac{(1+\sqrt{3}i)}{6}g_2 + \frac{2}{3}g_3
\end{aligned} \tag{197}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{14}g_1 &= \frac{2}{3}g_1 + \frac{5(1+\sqrt{3}i)}{12}g_2 + \frac{5(1-\sqrt{3}i)}{12}g_3 \\
D_{14}g_2 &= \frac{2(1-\sqrt{3}i)}{3}g_1 + \frac{2}{3}g_2 + \frac{(1+\sqrt{3}i)}{6}g_3 \\
D_{14}g_3 &= \frac{2(1+\sqrt{3}i)}{3}g_1 + \frac{(1-\sqrt{3}i)}{6}g_2 + \frac{2}{3}g_3
\end{aligned} \tag{198}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11}g_1 &= -2g_1 \\
D_{11}g_2 &= -2g_2 \\
D_{11}g_3 &= -2g_3
\end{aligned} \tag{199}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{22}g_1 &= -2g_1 \\
D_{22}g_2 &= -2g_2 \\
D_{22}g_3 &= -2g_3
\end{aligned} \tag{200}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{33}g_1 &= -2g_1 \\
D_{33}g_2 &= -2g_2 \\
D_{33}g_3 &= -2g_3
\end{aligned} \tag{201}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{44}g_1 &= -2g_1 \\
D_{44}g_2 &= -2g_2 \\
D_{44}g_3 &= -2g_3
\end{aligned} \tag{202}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
V^2g_1 &= 0 \\
V^2g_2 &= \frac{2i}{3\sqrt{3}}g_2 \\
V^2g_3 &= -\frac{2i}{3\sqrt{3}}g_3
\end{aligned} \tag{203}$$

Here below the observables on the respective basis elements.

5.5.2 Observables on the g_1 basis element

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11,g_1} &= -2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{dimensional } D_{11,g_1} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
D_{22,g_1} &= -2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{dimensional } D_{22,g_1} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
D_{33,g_1} &= -2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{dimensional } D_{33,g_1} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
D_{44,g_1} &= -2 \quad \textit{sharp} \\
\textit{dimensional } D_{44,g_1} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \textit{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{204}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{12} \rangle_{g_1} &= \frac{2}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{12} \rangle_{g_1} &= \frac{1}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{12} \rangle_{g_1} &= 70.5^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{12}, g_1} &= \frac{2\sqrt{5}}{3} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{12}, g_1} &= \frac{\sqrt{5}}{3} \approx 0.745 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{\sqrt{5}}{3} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{12, g_1} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{\sqrt{5}}{3} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{12, g_1} \leq 114.3^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{205}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{g_1} &= \frac{2}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{g_1} &= \frac{1}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{13} \rangle_{g_1} &= 70.5^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{13}, g_1} &= \frac{2\sqrt{5}}{3} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13}, g_1} &= \frac{\sqrt{5}}{3} \approx 0.745 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{\sqrt{5}}{3} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{13, g_1} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{\sqrt{5}}{3} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{13, g_1} \leq 114.3^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{206}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{g_1} &= \frac{2}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{14} \rangle_{g_1} &= \frac{1}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{14} \rangle_{g_1} &= 70.5^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{14}, g_1} &= \frac{2\sqrt{5}}{3} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{14}, g_1} &= \frac{\sqrt{5}}{3} \approx 0.745 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{\sqrt{5}}{3} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{14, g_1} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{\sqrt{5}}{3} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
0^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{14, g_1} \leq 114.3^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{207}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{g_1}^2 &= 0 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } V_{g_1}^2 &= 0 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{208}$$

5.5.3 Observables on the g_2 basis element

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11,g_2} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{11,g_2} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{22,g_2} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{22,g_2} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{33,g_2} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{33,g_2} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{44,g_2} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{44,g_2} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{209}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{12} \rangle_{g_2} &= \frac{2}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{12} \rangle_{g_2} &= \frac{1}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{12} \rangle_{g_2} &= 70.5^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{12},g_2} &= \frac{\sqrt{11}}{3} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{12},g_2} &= \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} \approx 0.553 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{12,g_2} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
27.6^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{12,g_2} \leq 102.7^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{210}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{g_2} &= \frac{2}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{g_2} &= \frac{1}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{13} \rangle_{g_2} &= 70.5^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{13},g_2} &= \frac{\sqrt{11}}{3} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13},g_2} &= \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} \approx 0.553 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{13,g_2} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
27.6^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{13,g_2} \leq 102.7^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{211}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{g_2} &= \frac{2}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{14} \rangle_{g_2} &= \frac{1}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{14} \rangle_{g_2} &= 70.5^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{14}, g_2} &= \frac{\sqrt{11}}{3} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{14}, g_2} &= \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} \approx 0.553 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{14, g_2} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
27.6^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{14, g_2} \leq 102.7^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{212}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{g_2}^2 &= \frac{2i}{3\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } V_{g_2}^2 &= -\frac{2}{3\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{213}$$

5.5.4 Observables on the g_3 basis element

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{11, g_3} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{11, g_3} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{22, g_3} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{22, g_3} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{33, g_3} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{33, g_3} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
D_{44, g_3} &= -2 \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } D_{44, g_3} &= 2a_0^2 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{214}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{12} \rangle_{g_3} &= \frac{2}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{12} \rangle_{g_3} &= \frac{1}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{12} \rangle_{g_3} &= 70.5^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{12}, g_3} &= \frac{\sqrt{11}}{3} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{12}, g_3} &= \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} \approx 0.553 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{12, g_3} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
27.6^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{12, g_3} \leq 102.7^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{215}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{13} \rangle_{g_3} &= \frac{2}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{13} \rangle_{g_3} &= \frac{1}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{13} \rangle_{g_3} &= 70.5^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{13}, g_3} &= \frac{\sqrt{11}}{3} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{13}, g_3} &= \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} \approx 0.553 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{13, g_3} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
27.6^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{13, g_3} \leq 102.7^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{216}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle D_{14} \rangle_{g_3} &= \frac{2}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\text{normalized } \langle D_{14} \rangle_{g_3} &= \frac{1}{3} \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\langle \text{angle}_{14} \rangle_{g_3} &= 70.5^\circ \quad \text{expectation value} \\
\sigma_{D_{14}, g_3} &= \frac{\sqrt{11}}{3} \\
\text{normalized } \sigma_{D_{14}, g_3} &= \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} \approx 0.553 \\
\frac{1}{3} - \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} &\leq \text{normalized } D_{14, g_3} \leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{\sqrt{11}}{6} \quad \text{fuzzy} \\
27.6^\circ &\leq \text{angle}_{14, g_3} \leq 102.7^\circ \quad \text{fuzzy}
\end{aligned} \tag{217}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{g_3}^2 &= -\frac{2i}{3\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{sharp} \\
\text{dimensional } V_{g_3}^2 &= \frac{2}{3\sqrt{3}} a_0^3 \quad \text{sharp}
\end{aligned} \tag{218}$$

5.6 A general spin network in the representation $(1, 1, 1, 1)$

Any spin network SN can be written as a linear combination of the elements of a basis. For instance, let's normalize the (u_0, u_1, u_2) basis

$$\begin{aligned} u'_0 &= \frac{u_0}{\sqrt{u_0^\dagger u_0}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} u_0 \\ u'_1 &= \frac{u_1}{\sqrt{u_1^\dagger u_1}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} u_1 \\ u'_2 &= \frac{u_2}{\sqrt{u_2^\dagger u_2}} = \frac{1}{3} u_2 \end{aligned} \tag{219}$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} u_0'^\dagger u'_0 &= 1 \\ u_1'^\dagger u'_1 &= 1 \\ u_2'^\dagger u'_2 &= 1 \\ u_0'^\dagger u'_1 &= 0 \\ u_0'^\dagger u'_2 &= 0 \\ u_1'^\dagger u'_2 &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{220}$$

i.e. (u'_0, u'_1, u'_2) is an orthonormal basis.

We have

$$\begin{aligned} SN &= d_0 u'_0 + d_1 u'_1 + d_2 u'_2 \\ SN^\dagger SN &= 1 \quad \text{normalization} \\ |d_0|^2 + |d_1|^2 + |d_2|^2 &= 1 \\ |d_0|^2 &= \cos^2(\theta) \\ |d_1|^2 &= \sin^2(\theta) \cos^2(\phi) \\ |d_2|^2 &= \sin^2(\theta) \sin^2(\phi) \\ d_0 &= \cos(\theta) \\ d_1 &= \sin(\theta) \cos(\phi) e^{i\alpha} \\ d_2 &= \sin(\theta) \sin(\phi) e^{i\beta} \end{aligned} \tag{221}$$

The coefficients, d_0 , d_1 and d_2 , are set considering that a quantum state is defined up to a common phase factor. Being the isotropic subspace 3-dimensional, a tetrahedron can not be described as a qubit any more. Note that $SN(\theta = 0) = u'_0$, $SN(\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}, \phi = 0) = u'_1$ and $SN(\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}, \phi = \frac{\pi}{2}) = u'_2$ (in the two latter, showing only one term, the phase factor is unessential).

6 Conclusions

A quantum tetrahedron is an open spin network with one node of valence 4. At the ground state (representation $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$) it exhibits an invariant isotropic subspace of dimension 2; therefore a general spin network can be described as a qubit. On the basis of the dihedral D_{12} one of the bases is flat, i.e. the tetrahedron is degenerate, however due to the quantum uncertainty the other dihedrals are spread around a non flat expectation value. The expectation value of the squared volume V^2 of both the bases vanishes, but the squared volume is spread between negative and positive values of the same magnitude. On the basis of the squared volume V^2 the two eigenvalues are equal in absolute value, but opposite in sign. The related two bases can be understood as two tetrahedra, of which one is the reflection of the other against one of the faces. They are two distinct geometric objects.

At the nearest excited state (representation $(1, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 1)$) a quantum tetrahedron shows dimension 2, as the ground state, and so is describable as a qubit as well. On the basis of the dihedral D_{12} , however, neither of the two bases is degenerate. As for the rest, it is similar to the ground state.

At the further near excited state (representation $(1, 1, 1, 1)$) a quantum tetrahedron manifests an invariant isotropic subspace of dimension 3; therefore a general spin network can not be described as a qubit any more. On the basis of the dihedral D_{12} one of the three bases is flat, i.e. the tetrahedron is degenerate, however due to the quantum uncertainty the other dihedrals are spread around a non flat expectation value. The expectation value of the squared volume V^2 of all the three bases vanishes, but the squared volume is spread between negative and positive values of the same magnitude. On the basis of the squared volume V^2 one of the three eigenvalues vanishes, i.e. the tetrahedron is degenerate, however due to the quantum uncertainty the dihedrals are spread around a non flat expectation value. As for the other two eigenvalues, they are equal in absolute value, but opposite in sign. The related bases of these two latter can be understood as two tetrahedra, of which one is the reflection of the other against one of the faces. They are two distinct geometric objects, confirming what already in the previous lower spin representations.

In the semiclassical (large spin) limit quantum physics is expected to match the sharpness of classical physics showing a progressive decrease in the fuzziness of the observables. At the Planck scale, for instance as for the spreading of the fuzzy dihedrals, the picture is still controversial. In fact, if we compare the representation $(1, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 1)$ against the representation $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$, we note a generalized reduction of the uncertainty; however the representation $(1, 1, 1, 1)$ displays discordant data. Nevertheless, also in this last case, the nondegenerate bases on the basis of the squared volume V^2 show a decreasing trend in the uncertainty of most of the dihedrals.

Appendix

A.1 Geometric meaning of a +ve/-ve dimensional squared volume

A classical tetrahedron ν is sketched in figure 13, where the outer normals to the faces are shown as well.

Figure 13: Classical tetrahedron (outer normals shown)

It has 6 sides and 4 outer normals, but only 3 sides are independent and only 3 normals are as well. As for the outer normals, I recall here the classical closure condition: $\sum_a \vec{l}_a = 0$, where $a = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

The relation between the sides and the outer normals presents

$$\begin{aligned}
 \vec{l}_1 &= -\frac{1}{2} s_{42} \times s_{43} & s_{41} &= \sqrt{2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}} \vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3 \\
 \vec{l}_2 &= -\frac{1}{2} s_{43} \times s_{41} & s_{42} &= \sqrt{2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}} \vec{l}_3 \times \vec{l}_1 \\
 \vec{l}_3 &= -\frac{1}{2} s_{41} \times s_{42} & s_{43} &= \sqrt{2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}} \vec{l}_1 \times \vec{l}_2
 \end{aligned} \tag{222}$$

where $d = |-\vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)|$

Note:

$$\begin{aligned}
 s_{41} \cdot (s_{42} \times s_{43}) &= -2\sqrt{2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}} (\vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)) \\
 V &= \frac{1}{6} |s_{41} \cdot (s_{42} \times s_{43})| = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} |-\vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)|^{1/2} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} d^{1/2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{223}$$

where V is the tetrahedron volume.

As $s_{41} \cdot (s_{42} \times s_{43}) > 0$ if the sequence x_1, x_2, x_3 is pictured as clockwise from x_4 , we have that the mixed product $\vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)$ is instead < 0 . Alternatively, if the sequence x_1, x_2, x_3 is pictured as anticlockwise from x_4 , the mixed product $\vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)$ is > 0 .

Therefore, if we write the squared volume as $V^2 = \frac{2}{9} \vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)$, it may assume positive or negative values. In the specific, the tetrahedron ν in figure 13 shows a clockwise sequence x_1, x_2, x_3 , hence a negative squared volume V^2 .

Now, let's reflect the x_3 vertex against the plane identified by the opposite face, thus reflecting the side s_{43} . The geometric properties of the reflected tetrahedron show as

$$\begin{aligned}
\vec{l}_{1\,refl}^2 &= \vec{l}_1^2 \\
\vec{l}_{2\,refl}^2 &= \vec{l}_2^2 \\
\vec{l}_{3\,refl}^2 &= \vec{l}_3^2 \\
\vec{l}_{4\,refl}^2 &= \vec{l}_4^2 \\
d_{12\,refl} &= \vec{l}_{1\,refl} \cdot \vec{l}_{2\,refl} = \vec{l}_1 \cdot \vec{l}_2 = d_{12} \\
d_{13\,refl} &= \vec{l}_{1\,refl} \cdot \vec{l}_{3\,refl} = \vec{l}_1 \cdot \vec{l}_3 = d_{13} \\
d_{14\,refl} &= \vec{l}_{1\,refl} \cdot \vec{l}_{4\,refl} = \vec{l}_1 \cdot \vec{l}_4 = d_{14} \\
V_{\nu\,refl}^2 &= -V_\nu^2
\end{aligned} \tag{224}$$

Note: $\vec{l}_{a\,refl}$ is not the reflection of \vec{l}_a , but it is the inner normal of the reflected face, resultant from equation (222) when s_{43} is replaced with $s_{43\,refl}$.

The reflected tetrahedron has the same squared areas and the same dihedral angles as the original tetrahedron, but the squared volume opposite in sign. As it is a reflection, it can not be obtained via a rotation, hence they are two different geometric objects.

The reflected tetrahedron is depicted in figure 14.

3

Figure 14: Reflected tetrahedron (inner normals shown)

Here below the calculations.

$$\begin{aligned} s_{43} &= s_{43\parallel} + s_{43\perp} \\ s_{43\text{refl}} &= s_{43\parallel} - s_{43\perp} \end{aligned} \tag{225}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{l}_1 &= -\frac{1}{2} s_{42} \times s_{43} = -\frac{1}{2} (s_{42} \times s_{43\parallel} + s_{42} \times s_{43\perp}) \\ \vec{l}_1^2 &= \vec{l}_1 \cdot \vec{l}_1 = \frac{1}{4} ((s_{42} \times s_{43\parallel})^2 + (s_{42} \times s_{43\perp})^2) \\ \vec{l}_{1\text{refl}} &= -\frac{1}{2} s_{42} \times s_{43\text{refl}} = -\frac{1}{2} (s_{42} \times s_{43\parallel} - s_{42} \times s_{43\perp}) \\ \vec{l}_{1\text{refl}}^2 &= \vec{l}_{1\text{refl}} \cdot \vec{l}_{1\text{refl}} = \frac{1}{4} ((s_{42} \times s_{43\parallel})^2 + (s_{42} \times s_{43\perp})^2) \end{aligned} \tag{226}$$

hence

$$\vec{l}_{1\text{refl}}^2 = \vec{l}_1^2$$

Note: $(s_{42} \times s_{43\parallel})$ is \perp to $(s_{42} \times s_{43\perp})$, so the scalar product is zero.

Similarly as for $\vec{l}_{2\text{refl}}$ and $\vec{l}_{4\text{refl}}$. Note that $\vec{l}_{3\text{refl}}$ is not affected by the reflection and it is the same as \vec{l}_3 .

$$\begin{aligned}
d_{12} &= \vec{l}_1 \cdot \vec{l}_2 = \frac{1}{4}(s_{42} \times s_{43}) \cdot (s_{43} \times s_{41}) = \\
&= \frac{1}{4}((s_{42} \times s_{43 \parallel}) \cdot (s_{43 \parallel} \times s_{41}) + (s_{42} \times s_{43 \perp}) \cdot (s_{43 \perp} \times s_{41})) \\
d_{12 \text{ refl}} &= \vec{l}_{1 \text{ refl}} \cdot \vec{l}_{2 \text{ refl}} = \frac{1}{4}(s_{42} \times s_{43 \text{ refl}}) \cdot (s_{43 \text{ refl}} \times s_{41}) = \\
&= \frac{1}{4}((s_{42} \times s_{43 \parallel}) \cdot (s_{43 \parallel} \times s_{41}) + (s_{42} \times s_{43 \perp}) \cdot (s_{43 \perp} \times s_{41}))
\end{aligned} \tag{227}$$

hence

$$d_{12 \text{ refl}} = d_{12}$$

Note: $(s_{42} \times s_{43 \parallel})$ is \perp to $(s_{43 \perp} \times s_{41})$, $(s_{42} \times s_{43 \perp})$ is \perp to $(s_{43 \parallel} \times s_{41})$, so the respective scalar products are zero.

Similarly as for $d_{13 \text{ refl}}$ and $d_{14 \text{ refl}}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
s_{41} \cdot (s_{42} \times s_{43}) &= s_{43} \cdot (s_{41} \times s_{42}) = (s_{43 \parallel} + s_{43 \perp}) \cdot (s_{41} \times s_{42}) = \\
&= s_{43 \perp} \cdot (s_{41} \times s_{42}) \\
s_{41} \cdot (s_{42} \times s_{43 \text{ refl}}) &= s_{43 \text{ refl}} \cdot (s_{41} \times s_{42}) = (s_{43 \parallel} - s_{43 \perp}) \cdot (s_{41} \times s_{42}) = \\
&= -s_{43 \perp} \cdot (s_{41} \times s_{42})
\end{aligned}$$

hence

$$s_{41} \cdot (s_{42} \times s_{43 \text{ refl}}) = -s_{41} \cdot (s_{42} \times s_{43}) \tag{228}$$

and

$$\vec{l}_{1 \text{ refl}} \cdot (\vec{l}_{2 \text{ refl}} \times \vec{l}_{3 \text{ refl}}) = -\vec{l}_1 \cdot (\vec{l}_2 \times \vec{l}_3)$$

so

$$V_{\nu \text{ refl}}^2 = -V_\nu^2$$

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